

Project:
ISABEL
 (Grand Agreement 691752)

"Triggering Sustainable Biogas Energy Communities through Social Innovation"

Funding Scheme: Coordination and Support Action
 Programme: HORIZON2020
 Societal Challenge: "Secure, clean and efficient energy"

D1.1 Social Innovation and Community Energy best practices, methods and tools across Europe

Issued by:	INSEAD, Social Innovation Centre
Issue date:	01/04/2016
Due date:	01/04/2016
Work Package Leader:	INSEAD, Social Innovation Centre

Start date of project: 01 January 2016

Duration: 36 months

Document History <i>(Revisions – Amendments)</i>	
Version and date	Changes
1.0 – 01/04/2016	Final version based on the results of the literature review and the semi-qualitative interviews with key stakeholders across Europe

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Main authors

- ✓ Prof. Craig Smith, Dr Stamatina Rassa (INSEAD project team)
- ✓ Mr Iakovos Delioglani, Mr Manthos Bougiouklis (Q-PLAN project team)
- ✓ Prof. Nigel Gilbert, Dr Alexandra Penn, Davide Poggio (SURREY project team)
- ✓ Mr. Birger Kerckow, Mr. Diego Piedra-Garcia (FNR project team)

LEGAL NOTICE

Neither the European Commission nor any person acting on behalf of the Commission is responsible for the use, which might be made, of the following information.

The views expressed in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Commission

© ISABEL Consortium, 2016

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged

Table of Contents

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
2.	SOCIAL INNOVATION CONCEPT AND PRACTICES.....	3
2.1	Why Social Innovation matters?	3
2.2	Examples of Social Innovation initiatives	5
2.2.1	The Fleet Management in Humanitarian Operations	5
2.2.2	The Global Healthcare Supply Chains: Learning from Coca-Cola	5
2.2.3	Bybi, the City Bee Project Enterprise in Copenhagen (Denmark)	6
2.2.4	La Petite Reine, Electric “Cargo-bikes” in Paris	7
2.2.5	Sutton Community Farm, London (UK)	7
3.	COMMUNITY ENERGY.....	8
3.1	Renewable Energy	8
3.2	Community energy is renewable energy.....	11
3.3	Examples of Community Energy initiatives	12
3.3.1	Austrian Güssing community biomass	12
3.3.2	Danish Samsø island	12
3.3.3	German Jühnde bioenergy village in Lower Saxony	13
4.	SOCIAL INNOVATION APPLIED TO COMMUNITY ENERGY	14
4.1	Social Innovation community driven examples	14
4.1.1	The Sustainable Social Shifts: SPREAD Sustainable Lifestyles 2050	14
4.1.2	Alternative Marketplace: ITC e-Choupal, in Bihar, India	14
4.2	Participatory methods and tools	15
5.	SUCCESS AND FAILURE FACTORS	17
6.	INTERVIEWS IN THE FIELD.....	19
6.1	Key findings and Observations	19
6.1.1	The Bioenergy & Environment Cluster of Western Macedonia (Clu.B.E.) - Greece	22
6.1.2	Energy Cooperative Company in Karditsa Prefecture (ECCK) - Greece	22
6.1.3	Bioenergy village Bollewick - Germany	23
6.1.4	Methanogen UK Ltd - UK	23
6.1.5	Community Energy Solutions in Orkney – Scotland, UK.....	24
6.1.6	Camphill Community Biogas Project at Ballytobin County Kilkenny in Ireland – Ireland.....	25
6.1.7	Malaby Biogas Plant – England, UK	26
6.1.8	Devon Community Composting Network – England, UK	27
6.1.9	Lymm Community Energy in Cheshire – England, UK	28
6.1.10	Municipal Energy Supplier Radolfzell (SWR) – Germany.....	29
6.1.11	District Heating Network Völkofen GmbH - Germany.....	29
6.1.12	Solarcomplex AG Supply Chain Bioenergy – Germany	30

6.1.13	Laconic Bioenergy SA - Greece	30
6.1.14	Spirit of Lanarkshire Wind Energy Cooperative Ltd – Scotland, UK	32
6.1.15	ZEZ Cooperative – Croatia	33
6.1.16	Danish Hashoej Biogas Cooperative – Denmark	34
6.1.17	SVEF is a wind power cooperative – Sweden	35
6.1.18	Sharenergy Consulting Co-op – UK.....	36
6.2	Best Practices.....	37
7.	CONCLUSIONS & IMPLICATIONS FOR BIOGAS	41
	APPENDIX 1: BASIC CONCEPTS OF SOCIAL INNOVATION	43
	APPENDIX 2: BEST PRACTICES IN RENEWABLE ENERGY (LITERATURE SURVEY)	45
	APPENDIX 3: INTERVIEW QUESTIONS	49

1. Executive Summary

*International energy production models are changing rapidly in response to the twin-pressures of climate change and declining fossil fuel reserves.¹ As a result, low-carbon economies, their management and ownership, have become increasingly important. **Community energy is a collective bottom-up approach to tackling challenges related to energy, sustainability and climate change**². Community energy projects engage local people to lead, control and benefit jointly from their venture. The challenge is to meet sustainability targets for secure energy systems, minimized greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), as well as for reduced individual and group heating and electricity bills. New models for innovation are needed to realise the potential of community energy projects.³*

Social innovation is a type of innovation that focuses on human factors. **Community energy** is a community based venture for generating and owning renewable energy. The combination of social innovation and community energy can create a new bottom-up approach to developing new alternative energy marketplaces (in the sense of entering the renewable energy market) with diverse impacts, i.e. social, environmental and financial. Community-generated and -owned renewable energy at the local and regional scale is a potential local-scale solution to the long-standing global problem associated with energy depletion and inefficient use of resources.

The challenge for ISABEL, is that the definitions, practices, methods and tools to carry out such schemes are complex and do not follow a “single prescription to success” concept. They combine numerous powerful socio-economic and political attributes and although some of them may seem to borrow elements from a diverse number of sectors, they translate, in effect, into new projects that cannot be easily replicated.

Therefore, the main purpose of this report is to explore and identify a number of *practices, methods and tools* in applying social innovation in community energy projects across Europe. In this analysis **we explore examples of cases, methods and good practices** that could inform future, successful renewable energy models and socially responsive ways to deliver social programs and partnerships across Europe. Complementing this use of secondary sources is **an empirical study of relevant initiatives based on 18 semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, which** examines their understanding, experience and views of what makes for a successful social innovation community energy project, what are the obstacles, and how they can be addressed.

The analysis of important attributes of social innovation in community energy practices suggests that the socio-economic motives for such projects can be stronger than the environmental ones. Our interviews show additionally that community-based organizations often create entirely new market structures (with their own supply chains and operational characteristics). Creating a new renewable energy marketplace is the challenge, which does not only focus on creating new products (e.g. an electric-bike in Paris) but more importantly focuses on **raising awareness, creating incentives, educating and connecting different stakeholders** (citizens, municipalities, policymakers). Through the involvement of stakeholders in such projects, investments in new renewable community energy projects can be empowered.

Successful social innovations applied to community energy projects create alternative marketplaces that trigger consumer behavioural changes. This can be by following a number of methods and utilising various tools (such as social media, and social gaming). Behavioural changes can also be triggered through

¹ <http://demandthefuture.tumblr.com/post/116569218190/demand-33-community-energy-put-the-energy>

² <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/community-energy>

³ Clinton, L. & Whisnant, R. (2014), *Model Behavior: 20 Business Model Innovations for Sustainability*, SustainAbility Ltd. (www.sustainability.com)

cooperatives (playing a direct role in profit generation and sharing) and **energy ownership, shared-resources and micro-franchising**.⁴ The provision of **inclusive sourcing** (that engages small farming companies in larger corporations) can also contribute towards the creation of new market connections, increase farmer learning and benefit the large corporations' legitimacy in local markets by enabling branding of their products as "ethical"⁵ (e.g. Walmart cut out channel intermediaries and enabled direct supply from farmers, which increased the farmers' income by 10-15%). Financial innovations are strongly related to social and community energy innovations and can translate in crowd funding approaches to alternative ideas and thus attract investments for community energy purposes.

The interview findings represent viewpoints of stakeholders from numerous European nations (including Greece, Germany, UK, Croatia, Denmark and Sweden). Remarkably, these diverse viewpoints suggest that there are three main factors which can influence the success of a social innovation community energy project. These points are also consistent with our literature review. The three factors highlighted are **communication, partnership, and socio-economic benefits**.

More specifically, **communication** can inform people (through face-to-face or via technologically advanced methods, e.g. social media and social gaming) about the importance of entering jointly in a new alternative energy marketplace, local core competencies and geographical capacities. It can *raise awareness* and also *educate people*, as well as *increase transparency* in the methods that are proposed to be followed in order to implement a successful, sustainable and profitable community energy project. Successful examples of already implemented projects can be shared in communication settings, where successful "*role model*" (prototype) projects can be demonstrated. Role models can increase public trust and engagement in a new venture for energy efficiency. Interestingly, the interviewed stakeholders suggested that communication is a key method for tackling challenges or obstacles during renewable energy projects.

Partnerships are another important factor that can stimulate the initiation of community energy projects. These should join sectors, such as the public, private (e.g. planning, bioenergy networks), NGOs, and academic sectors. It may be that only through joining forces can a project be successful. However, this relates directly to **socio-economic benefits** that can strengthen stakeholder motivation, engagement, and investment. These benefits relate mostly to the so-called *financial "sweeteners"* for becoming local energy shareholders (e.g. tax reliefs and subsidies)—as described in one of the ISABEL interviews.

Community energy projects empower local communities not only to generate and export their own energy but also to reinvest part of the profits into the community. This method promotes **self-sufficiency** and a sense of community engagement in a "common good" through the use of new technologies that can enhance lifestyles. It also stimulates leadership and highlights the involvement of community members in local and regional **decision-making**. The latter can assist in tackling long-standing obstacles, which may, for example, stem from inflexible government legislation.

Finally, in exploring the implications of social innovation for biogas community energy, it has been identified that bioenergy does not serve only as a new alternative energy source (by the use of biomass and organic waste), but also supports **local farmers' entrepreneurship, local cooperatives** and the creation of local **nutrient banks**. It has been suggested that biogas use offers a **healthy, financially viable and environmentally sustainable alternative energy** that can fuel vehicles, heat communities and light up streets. It is versatile and can be locally available. It can minimize greenhouse gas emissions and also create job opportunities. Therefore ISABEL proposes to pursue and exploit biogas as a socio-economic and environmental "common good" for the communities of today and the future.

⁴ Ibid ³

⁵ Ibid ³

2. Social Innovation concept and practices

The term "**innovation**" can be defined as something original and more effective and, as a consequence, new, that "breaks into" the market or society⁶. **Social innovation** is the introduction of new business models and market-based mechanisms that deliver sustainable economic, environmental and social prosperity.

-INSEAD, Social Innovation Centre⁷

2.1 Why Social Innovation matters?

Source⁸

Ever since the discovery of fire, humans have worked to improve their lives through innovation (Global Innovation Index⁹), which is based on novel ideas, effective devices and methods or processes, services and technologies¹⁰. Some of these ideas have been value creators and may offer incremental changes (e.g. introducing a new feature in a consumer product). Innovation can be multifaceted and according to the INSEAD Prof. Soumitra Dutta, **the essential element for a successful innovation is the innovation readiness or maturity of an organization,**

which refers to an organizational capacity to realize a specific cutting-edge practical topic¹¹. Without this type of readiness, investments can face the threat of being wasted. **Introducing a human factor in innovations creates Social Innovation** (Dutta et al. 2014¹²). Social innovation has a social impact.

Although legislations and policies exist to tackle numerous specific issues of social life, experience has shown that some of the most pressing social challenges are multivariate and thus complex to tackle through predetermined legal operations, rules and procedures. Social innovation is a powerful way of tackling complex social challenges and problems **by combining the strengths of multiple stakeholders (cross-sector) in order to develop original solutions for pressing social needs**. Social innovation can be conceived, planned and executed by governments, agencies, NGOs, charities, businesses, Universities, philanthropists, or combinations of the above¹³. **Its nature is participatory and aims at achieving societal behavioural changes towards sustainability or a 'public good'** (e.g. the implementation of a new biogas community energy project).

An early discussion of social innovation can be found in the work of Drucker & Young in the 1960s¹⁴. Five decades later, there is still a lack of sufficient theoretical and empirical evidence on the definition, exact methods and tools for social innovation. **The main challenge in carrying out social innovation projects is that there is no standard and uniformly advisable approach to tackle problems**. That is due to the complexity and breadth of the problems raised. The tendency for social innovation is to follow organic multivariate approaches, often by borrowing and combining a variety of existing strategies. Each project has different characteristics and needs, thus it is common that **social innovations are "tailor-made"** (developed according to each individual case).

⁶Based on Frankelius, P. (2009). "Questioning two myths in innovation literature". *Journal of High Technology Management Research*. Vol. 20, No. 1, pp. 40–51.

⁷ https://www.insead.edu/facultyresearch/centres/isic/home/about_us.cfm

⁸ Ibid ³

⁹ <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org/content/page/GII-Home>

¹⁰ <http://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/innovation>

¹¹ http://innovationmanagement.se/images/stories/file/INSEAD_report.pdf

¹² <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org/content/page/GII-Home>

¹³ Biggs, R., Westley, F.R. & Carpener, S.R. (2010). Navigating the Back Loop: Fostering Social Innovation and Transformation in Ecosystem Management. *Ecology and Society*. 15:2 (9).

¹⁴ <http://www.paristechreview.com/2011/12/16/social-innovation-future-economy/>

Social innovation is particularly applicable in tackling global issues, such as these of climate change, poverty and sustainability¹⁵. It is strongly linked to the environment challenges and their impacts on peoples' lives, health and wellbeing. That is because environmental disasters can instigate numerous social repercussions, such as waste causing pollution and thereafter impacting on public health. Eco-friendly social innovation and environmental incentives contribute to sustainable development processes, such as renewable energy use, wastewater treatment and more.

EFFECTIVE SOCIAL INNOVATION

According to SustainAbility¹⁶, some important social innovation practices are the so-called “buy one, give one”, “cooperative ownership” and “inclusive sourcing” models. The “**buy one, give one**” practice refers to selling a product or a service and thereafter re-investing part of the profit in similar services that are needed. The “**cooperative ownership**” is an operational model through which, industries take into account the broader concerns and interests of local stakeholders, such as these of the local community and the environment. “**Inclusive sourcing**” relates to including and supporting a local farmer or producer community in a specific industrial supply chain. Providing a bottom-up approach to social innovation relates also the factors illustrated on the table below¹⁷.

Base of the Pyramid	
Building a Marketplace	Companies build new markets for their products in innovative and socially responsible ways, including delivering social programs, adapting to local markets, and bundling with other services like microfinance and technical assistance
Differential Pricing	Realizing customers may benefit from the same product but have different payment thresholds, companies charge more to those who can afford it in order to subsidize those who cannot.
Microfinance	Providing small loans—and in some cases access to financial services—to low-income borrowers who do not have access to a traditional bank account.
Micro-Franchise	Leveraging the basic concepts of traditional franchising, but specifically focusing on creating opportunities for the poor to own and manage their own businesses.
Diverse Impact	
Alternative Marketplace	When a firm circumvents a traditional method of transaction or invents a new type of transaction to unleash untapped value.
Behaviour Change	Using a business model to stimulate behaviour change to reduce consumption, change purchasing patterns or modify daily habits
Product as a Service	Consumers pay for the service a product provides without the responsibility of repairing, replacing or disposing of it
Shared Resource	Enabling customers to access a product, rather than own it, and use it only as needed; often dependent on the participation and generosity of community members to share their goods with others

In the environmental sector, there are two important methods to innovate, one which relies on a specific material use that can create a continuously recyclable product (**closed-loop production**) and another which helps towards the development of new products from recovered waste (**re-materialization**). Thus these would seem to offer important factors in the bioenergy social innovation sector.

¹⁵ Ibid ³

¹⁶ Ibid ³

¹⁷ Ibid ³

2.2 Examples of Social Innovation initiatives

2.2.1 The Fleet Management in Humanitarian Operations¹⁸

Social Innovation Centre
© Luk N. Van Wassenhove 2011

Case: In the humanitarian sector, transportation is one of the two most important factors of their supply chain, services and operations (the most important being the personnel). While every year, \$ 1 billion is spent for the international field vehicle fleet, systems of logistics, which are decentralized, impede with the optimal performance of national programs¹⁹. Financial rewards and penalties are not considered as viable options. The problem is on the management side and related complicated information asymmetries due to the geographical disperse of Programs, National Logistics and Headquarter²⁰.

Method: The fleet management project analysed field vehicle fleet management in 4 large international humanitarian organizations (IHOs): the International Committee as well as the International Federation of the Red Cross, the World Food Program and the World Vision International. Aiming to identify their methods, critical factors and delivery programs, 40 interviews were administered at regional and national headquarters of these IHOs (in Africa, Europe & Middle East).

Practice (Best or Good): Implementing a new operation mechanism design for fleet management coordination. This mechanism proposed a new operational combination that coordinated different incentives and namely, policies and their role) as well as IHO Headquarter procedures. Finally, it suggested that a segmentation of services (whereby each IHO headquarter would offer fleet buffers as well as logistics) would focus only on the policies and procedures defined by their own headquarters²¹.

2.2.2 The Global Healthcare Supply Chains: Learning from Coca-Cola²²

Case: One of the most common questions in the humanitarian sector is: “How can Coca-Cola be found in the most remote locations of sub-Saharan Africa and anti-malaria medication cannot?”²³

Method: In order to identify the distribution procedures, which should be implemented in order to promote an effective global healthcare supply chain, INSEAD has analysed Coca-Cola’s supply chain. The purpose of this examination was to compare and further identify the best methods in distributing and expanding global healthcare in the developing context (e.g. sub-Saharan Africa)²⁴.

Practice (Best or Good): Coca-Cola’s model for global production and distribution offers ideas that can be borrowed but equally cannot be replicated. Therefore, the practice that was put forward was based on the concept of launching a new product and industry partnerships that could target remote and neglected sections of the world. These

¹⁸ <http://www.insead.edu/facultyresearch/research/doc.cfm?did=44315>

¹⁹ Ibid¹⁹

²⁰ https://www.insead.edu/facultyresearch/centres/isic/humanitarian/documents/WP2010-87_AnOperationalMechanismDesignforFleetManagementCoordinationinHumanitarianOperations.pdf

²¹ Ibid²¹

²² Yadav, P., Stapleton, O. & Van Wassenhove, L. (2013), “Learning from Coca-Cola”, *Stanford Social Innovation Review* (Available: www.ssireview.org)

²³ Ibid²³

²⁴ Ibid²²

partnerships included private pharmaceutical companies, public institutions and private philanthropic organizations that sponsored and supported pharmaceutical research and development (R&D). These new Product Development Partnerships (PDPs; since 1999)²⁵ were developed to produce drugs for diseases occurring in neglected areas of the developing world and involved a new venture called “Medicines for Malaria Venture” (MMV; which, 7 years after its establishment, undertook the issue of not only discovering and developing new drugs but also delivering them). MMV, which operates alike a “virtual company”, is a public-private partnership, which took a clear strategy to accessing and delivering malaria drugs to patients in endemic countries. This strategy builds on the WHO and Health Action International to access prices, availability and supply chains and effectively structure their works according to the structure of the anti-malarial market in African countries. Following this practice, MMV is able to ensure access to anti-malarial across the most remote and the poorest regions of the world²⁶.

2.2.3 *Bybi, the City Bee Project Enterprise in Copenhagen (Denmark)*

Bybi, promotes a greener urban model, developing an urban honey enterprise and, at the same time, giving jobs to homeless and long unemployed members of the society

Source²⁷

Case: Bees provide a very special service to the ecosystem as they induce pollination in agricultural environments and therefore food production. Although their contribution is vital for our ecosystems and our societies, little is being done to introduce this issue in an urban context. Bybi was founded by the anthropologist Oliver Maxwell who developed this social enterprise in the UK (in 2004) and thereafter in Denmark (in 2010²⁸). The concept of this project has been to promote prosperity without growth²⁹.

Method: Raising awareness towards environmental sustainability and resolving the social problem of unemployment. The project created a new generation of urban beekeepers, attracted participation from the community, provided new job opportunities and overall offered a new understanding of city life.

Practice (Best or Good): This project brought together citizens, businesses and municipalities. After three seasons of this enterprise, the level of honey production increased by approximately five times. All profits were invested back into the social and environmental activities, thus balancing the project socio-environmental objectives through an overarching financial sustainability.

²⁵ Ibid ²²

²⁶ Ibid ²²

²⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/integration/research/newsalert/pdf/IR10_en.pdf

²⁸ Ibid ²⁸

²⁹ www.sd-commission.org.uk/publications.php?id=914

2.2.4 La Petite Reine, Electric “Cargo-bikes” in Paris

La Petite Reine, electric “cargo-bikes” provides a new sustainable inner-city delivery service, currently operating in Paris, Bordeaux, Toulouse, Aix-en-Provence.

Source³⁰

(greenhouse gas) and is operated by people who have little education or professional experience. It is thus, both a socially and environmentally sustainable community incentive. All profits of the “cargo-bikes” are re-invested in the project.

Case: Paris has demonstrated a growing traffic-issue involving large trucks and other delivery services operating during peak hours. This issue is associated to rising pollution. Trucks are often very large and half-empty. In addition amongst the Paris population high levels of unemployment are demonstrated.

Method: A new method to minimize traffic and unemployment has identified through the development of the off-peak inner-city delivery “cargo-bike”(introduced in 2001). This is an electric, lightweight three-wheeled bike with a large storage cabin (1.5 m³), which transports goods of approximately 180kg merchandise³¹ during off-peak hours. This bike emits zero GHG

Practice (Best or Good): This project brought together local stakeholders, companies and authorities. The Petite Reine incentive involved specifically a private company-founder of la Petite Reine, a large French home delivery company (Star service), local authorities and retailers (Nicolas, BHV and Monoprix). The idea of an electrical bicycle for urban freight is now spreading around the world (e.g. in Brazil and USA).

2.2.5 Sutton Community Farm, London (UK)

Sutton Community Farm is London’s largest sustainable community farm, which not only offers organic products (fruits and vegetables) to the community but also a wider social and economic sustainability.

Source³²

Case: Cultivating land by minimizing GHG (greenhouse gas emissions), is a major challenge in agriculture nowadays. Working towards a more sustainable future in food production and supply, the borough of Sutton established the first “One Planet Community”³³ (in 2008).

Method: The ethos of the community-farm is to support community-owned agriculture. That is by purchasing non-profit shares, which nominate community members as stakeholders in the farm.

Practice (Best or Good): This was organized by the Bioregional international entrepreneurial charity and WWF and it achieved a reduction in GHG emissions through the three-step approach of transport, packaging and processing. Overall, the farm, apart from its ecological benefits, offers social benefits, as the community gains awareness (through apprenticeships and tutorials) and knowledge regarding the health benefits of producing and eating organic food.

³⁰ http://www.bestfact.net/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/CL1_QuickInfo_La%20Petite%20Reine-22Jan2014.pdf

³¹ Ibid ²⁸

³² <http://suttoncommunityfarm.org.uk/projects/sustainable-farming-assistant-programme>

³³ Ibid ²⁸

3. Community Energy

3.1 Renewable Energy

Acknowledging the business benefits of improved product performance, some have revamped their offerings to be more effective, more efficient and produced with safer, “greener” materials. Other companies have rethought their processes—for example, by utilizing renewable energy sources in production or enhancing performance and trust through various certifications.

SustainAbility, 2014³⁴

Climate change poses one of the greatest contemporary environmental and socio-economic challenges worldwide. While the impacts are attracting a rising global interest globally³⁵, its harmful results show no signs of significant decline, with EU-28 being the third largest CO₂ emitter globally (3420 MTn of CO₂ emitted in 2014³⁶)³⁷.

EU-28 being the third largest CO₂ emitter globally (3420 MTn of CO₂ emitted in 2014) (Source³⁸)

Adapting and mitigating the negative impacts of climate change was associated, in 2011, by the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)³⁹ with the use of renewable energy sources.

³⁴ Ibid ³

³⁵ <http://www.wri.org/indc-definition>

³⁶ <http://infographics.pbl.nl/website/globalco2-2015/>

³⁷ https://royalsociety.org/~media/Royal_Society_Content/policy/projects/climate-evidence-causes/climate-change-evidence-causes.pdf

³⁸ Ibid ³⁷

³⁹ <http://srren.ipcc-wg3.de/report>

162 parties submitted their INDCs in preparation for the adoption of the Paris Agreement in December 2015. These countries represented about 94% of global greenhouse gas emissions in 2012.

Map of 162 parties who submitted their INDCs by November 2015 (Source⁴⁰)

Renewable sources can provide energy for transportation, the generation of electricity, heating, cooling (through the use of air and/or water) as well as promote rural energy (off-grid)⁴¹. More specifically, it can contribute towards the overarching **2020 EU Directive** (2009/28/EC) for a 20% share of renewable energy use, within the total energy mix⁴² and a 10% share of renewable energy use for transport^{43,44}. In the following 15-years (2030), it is also anticipated that an additional 27% (or higher) of the energy mix should be led by renewable energy use in transport and low-carbon technologies (which could further attract private investments in infrastructure). This way, it is expected that Europe will ensure higher climate protection, energy security and renewable energy technology advancement as well as leadership⁴⁵. According to the EU Directives, technology leadership incentives can offer opportunities for EU industries to engage with the sustainable and low-carbon economy.

While Europe currently holds almost half of the renewable energy capacity worldwide (2012 figures stated this capacity to reach 44% of the global⁴⁶; the latter excludes the use of hydropower) and approximately 40% of the global patents on renewable energy⁴⁷, the problem of energy efficiency and sustainability remains widely unsolved.

The main benefits of its use are on the environmental sustainability and social welfare, as it cannot only offer a good practice for reducing imported energy sources, but also can provide knowledge, incentives for innovation and sustainability (e.g. in the energy and technology sector) as well as increase job opportunities (2020 target to create approx. 600,000 new jobs)⁴⁸.

Thus, the largest clean energy source⁴⁹ is the **sun**, which can produce thermal energy by the use of technologies, such as solar PVs (photovoltaic). The **wind**, **rainwater** and **ocean** as well as **biomass** (a

⁴⁰ Ibid ³⁷

⁴¹ http://www.harbertaxgroup.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/REN21_GSR_2010_full_revised-Sept2010.pdf

⁴² <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/renewable-energy>

⁴³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028>

⁴⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/renewable-energy>

⁴⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/renewable-energy>

⁴⁶ http://www.europarl.europa.eu/atyourservice/en/displayFtu.html?ftuld=FTU_5.7.4.html

⁴⁷ Ibid ⁴⁷

⁴⁸ <http://www.cost.eu/module/download/54801>

⁴⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/renewable-energy>

derivative of a number of different types of organic matter, such as plants, oilseeds, agro-waste and urban organic waste) can offer significant renewable energy sources and remarkable alternatives to oil and gas use as well as fossil fuels (which are high greenhouse gas emitters⁵⁰).

source: IEA, 2014; BP, 2015

The share of biomass amongst the new renewable energy, low-carbon energy and fossil fuels
(Source⁵¹)

Organic waste represents approximately 1/3 of the EU Municipal Solid Waste⁵². The EU produces approximately 75 to 100 MTn of organic waste per year (from food, gardens). The use of biomass for bioenergy and biofuels can have a wider environmental impact on minimizing greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to agro-environmental activities and more. It offers an alternative fuel for transportation. Liquid biofuels and biodiesel are expected to be the main contributors towards the EU Directive 2009/28/EC for a 10% share of renewable energy for transport⁵³. In 2010, bioenergy and biofuels contributed a significant amount of renewable energy in the EU-27 (63%⁵⁴, that equates to around 2,600 PJ). According to the EU National Renewable Energy Action Plan (NREAP) it is anticipated that the bioenergy and biofuel contribution will double⁵⁵ (2020 target to reach approx. 5880 PJ from bioenergy and biofuels).

Remarkably the use of biomass and its anaerobic digestion for the production of biogas is not new. Biogas has been used since the ancient times (by Persian, Chinese and Assyrian). In 1895, UK (Exeter) street-lights and homes were powered from sewage, wood gas and coal. Since 2005, Sweden offers a biogas-powered train service. Sweden, Switzerland, Germany the UK and Denmark are a few nations that currently use biogas for a variety of purposes (e.g. heating, transportation). Recently, the Greek EBZ sugar industry has converted 2 out of its 5 factories (in Thrace and Thessaly) to produce bioethanol⁵⁶. This and related technology has received an international interest and there are companies that feed with biodiesel truck fleets in Germany, Austria, Italy as well as barges passing from the port of Hamburg. Latest data also revealed that in the period 2013-2014, the EU-28 that has been a 6.1% increase in biofuel consumption (Biofuel barometer 2015; <http://www.eurobserv-er.org/biofuels-barometer-2015/>).

⁵⁰ http://www.europarl.europa.eu/atyourservice/en/displayFtu.html?ftuld=FTU_5.7.4.html

⁵¹ <http://infographics.pbl.nl/website/globalco2-2015/>

⁵² <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/compost/index.htm>

⁵³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028>

⁵⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/biofuels-and-bioenergy>

⁵⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/renewable-energy/national-action-plans>

⁵⁶ <http://ecology-salonika.org/2009/?p=393>

3.2 Community energy is renewable energy

Source⁵⁷

*Community energy is low carbon and renewable heat and power. It is produced locally and distributed via a heat network or private wire arrangement. As it is produced close to where it's needed, community energy reduces transmission losses and, over the longer term, lowers the cost of energy.*⁵⁸

*A sustainable community energy system is an integrated approach to supplying a local community with its energy requirements from renewable energy or high-efficiency co-generation energy sources. The approach can be seen as a development of the distributed generation concept.*⁵⁹

During the last few years, in Germany, individuals, farmer and municipalities produce a very large proportion of their national energy through renewable energy sources. There are more than 600 renewable energy cooperatives and local groups that produce electricity, some of which produce their local community-owned energy⁶⁰. Renewable energy cooperatives however do not only support middle-class incentives but also offer a meaningful outreach to low-income communities. That is by providing a new opportunity for local energy production and ownership. These initiatives offer a new energy market, which informs national schemes such as those of the UK⁶¹. The benefit of community energy is that it can support energy efficient solutions both in cases of retrofitting projects and new developments. **Community energy can empower local communities to develop new smart transition models, from dependent energy intensive demands, to new independently managed renewable energy supply chains**⁶².

WHY COMMUNITY ENERGY?

Remarkably, although climate change is an important driver for the use of renewable energy, surveys reveal that **community energy security and affordability** (saving energy and saving local expenses) may act as stronger motivators for community energy projects⁶³ for reasons of **minimizing local expenses for energy imports and exports** (by generating energy locally, minimizing energy bills and receiving tax reliefs or subsidies) as well as **maximizing regional benefits** (by stimulating investment in bioenergy projects, supporting the development regional markets (e.g. for solid biomass⁶⁴), supporting businesses of local Stakeholders, inspiring other rural areas to follow the example of the target regions that offers the potential of expanding local entrepreneurial activities and creating new job opportunities).

The community energy *challenge* is that community energy projects vary considerably (may be organized differently, using different methods, technologies or financial models) and there is no “single prescription to success”. However, all projects have the same goal. That is to ensure new affordable solutions for energy efficiency.

In the UK, during the last 5 years, more than 5,000 community energy initiatives have been developed. These community energy initiatives focus in renewable energy technologies, installations, energy generation and management across the nation. The UK Department of Energy & Climate Change⁶⁵ provides guidance for local communities that wish to generate and manage their own energy. This guidance focuses on community

⁵⁷ <http://demandthefuture.tumblr.com/post/116569218190/demand-33-community-energy-put-the-energy>

⁵⁸ <https://www.eonenergy.com/for-your-business/community-energy/what-is-community-energy>

⁵⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainable_community_energy_system

⁶⁰ Ibid⁵⁸

⁶¹ Ibid⁵⁸

⁶² Ibid⁵⁸

⁶³ <http://snapshotsfromberlin.com/2014/04/10/germanys-bioenergy-villages/>

⁶⁴ <http://www.bioregions.eu>

⁶⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/community-energy>

energy strategies and provides information on, for instance, community-owned electricity generation through harvesting solar (photovoltaic panels), wind (wind turbines) and hydroelectric power, generating heating by the use of biomass boilers and heat pumps and selecting collectively the community gas suppliers.

Although there is no “single prescription to success” of a project, it has identified (through literature review) that some important factors for *successful* community energy projects are that **local citizens should engage actively in their community energy decision-making process. They should also own**, if not completely at least partially, **renewable energy resources** (e.g. biomass) **and engage with the sustainable growth and harvesting processes.** Community energy needs (at least 50% of the total heating and electricity) should be covered by locally produced renewable energy (e.g. bioenergy) and finally, locally generated benefits (resources) should potentially be extendable at a wider regional scale.

3.3 Examples of Community Energy initiatives

3.3.1 Austrian Güssing community biomass

The Austrian Güssing community biomass is the first bioenergy village project in the European Union to have achieved a 90% decrease in its CO₂ emissions.

Source⁶⁶

Case: In Austria, community energy strategies have been pursued and pioneered since the mid-90s. The Güssing village⁶⁷ is a particularly successful example of these strategies and thus has received wide publicity (e.g. New York Times, 2007), as being the first biomass community energy project in the European Union to have achieved a 90% decrease in its total CO₂ emissions⁶⁸. The town currently has 60 new renewable energy companies and offers 1,500 new jobs. This precedent has motivated the development of more than 15 energy independent regions in Austria (aiming for electricity, heating and or transport service independence through renewable energy use).

Method: The Austrian Güssing village biomass community energy initiative offers a new sustainable forestry practice that runs by the use of wood chips and wood thinned from the forest as well as by the use of waste wood that from the local wood flooring company.

Practice (Best or Good): This project was initiated by local citizens, who noticed that the wood that was decomposing in the forest could be used as an energy source (for heating). With the support of the federal government Güssing has installed the first biomass gasification power plant of its kind in the world.

3.3.2 Danish Samsø island

Danish Samsø Island is a 100% renewable (wind) community energy initiative.

Source⁶⁹

Case: Samsø (which includes 22 villages)⁷⁰ nowadays covers locally the total amount of its electricity needs (suggested in literature to be 100%)⁷¹ as well as supports 20% of the national ones. Samsø is the largest single type of renewable energy generation and offers an exemplary case for implementation in other nations, such as in the U.S. The benefit of this initiative is that the inhabitants of the island have managed to eliminate their CO₂ emissions by producing and consuming renewable energy. In addition to the wind energy generation, biomass, straw and hot water boilers as well as heat

⁶⁶ http://blog.rmi.org/blog_2013_10_08_high-renewables_tomorrow_today_gussing_austria

⁶⁷ Ibid ⁶⁷

⁶⁸ Ibid ⁶⁷

⁶⁹ <http://www.decentralized-energy.com/articles/2015/12/danish-island-community-goes-100-per-cent-renewable.html>

⁷⁰ <http://www.scientificamerican.com/article/samsø-attempts-100-percent-renewable-power/>

⁷¹ Ibid ⁷⁰

pumps supply district heating to the Samsø households (75% of which are connected for heat supply purposes)⁷².

Method: Power generation comes from the use of 21 offshore wind turbines.

Practice (Best or Good): The partnership between citizens and municipality of Samsø as well as the Danish Government, local and external businesses led to the development of the Samsø renewable energy project. Achieving to develop a self-sufficient energy island has been based on the community initiative, which involved all 4,000 inhabitants of the island who nowadays generate their own power for electricity.

3.3.3 German Jühnde bioenergy village in Lower Saxony

The German Jühnde bioenergy village in Lower Saxony is the first bioenergy village in Germany that was developed in 2005 and currently produces twice the energy it consumes.

Source⁷³

Case: The notion that a community, a neighbourhood or a village can produce its own energy is not new in Germany⁷⁴. A highly successful (in terms of its profitability) community energy example is a cooperative project in Germany through which the community generates and sells its own energy to third parties. This cooperative community energy system appears currently in 1,000 locations across Germany.

Method: Based on the guidelines of the German Ministry of Food and Agriculture⁷⁵, the main criteria for the establishment of bio-energy villages relate to an overall challenge of combining land-use management and civic engagement and covering at least 50% of the energy needs (heat & electricity) from regionally sources biomass. That is in order to achieve to increase energy efficiency through local production of electricity and heating. This village produces its own heating and electricity, which is supplied by a local biogas plant sourced by local fuels. This village produces twice the energy it consumes and currently there are more than 150 bio-energy villages⁷⁶ in Germany that follow this example.

Practice (Best or Good): Jühnde is a village of 780 inhabitants. The cooperative that owns the local energy supply system (incl. heating grid) is populated by 195 members. Biogas electricity and heat are mainly produced by manure from 450 cows and energy crops, by the use of a woodchip boiler provided as a backup solution. The heat is distributed via a district heating network, which connects 144 households. The project was sponsored mainly by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (through the Agency for Renewable Resources), FNR, the federal state of Lower Saxony as well as by the district of Göttingen. This project was based on partnerships between local financial institutes, consulting engineers, building companies and scientific institutes.

⁷² Ibid ⁶⁹

⁷³ <http://www.greenbuildingadvisor.com/blogs/dept/guest-blogs/germany-s-bioenergy-villages>

⁷⁴ Ibid ⁷³

⁷⁵ Ibid ⁷³

⁷⁶ <http://www.wege-zum-bioenergiendorf.de>

4. Social Innovation Applied to Community Energy

4.1 Social Innovation community driven examples

There are numerous examples across Europe of social innovations that highlight environmental benefits of renewable energy use and sustainable development. Successful social innovation projects appeal generally to a wide range of stakeholders. Some successful (in terms of their resilience, adaptability and potential to diffuse⁷⁷) social innovation community driven examples (including their utilized methods and tools) are presented in more detail below.

4.1.1 The Sustainable Social Shifts: SPREAD⁷⁸ Sustainable Lifestyles 2050

Case: Co-housing is a residential model for saving energy by living around a common house. It has proved to achieve social shifts across European nations as it demonstrated ways to promote sustainable lifestyles through community action plans for eco-towns and co-housing. These plans originated from Scandinavia in the 1960s and further spread to the UK, Italy and Denmark.

Method: This is a shared resources model, which enables dwellers to share their co-housing facilities without necessarily owning them. This promotes a community interdependence, participation and generosity. Co-housing⁸⁰ provides the residents with a new way of managing their own community activities and energy. The co-housing model uses renewable energy for electricity and heating through small-scale sustainable technologies, such as rainwater harvesting.

Source⁷⁹

Practice (Best or Good): This project involves the participation of a wide range of stakeholders and local cooperatives to support energy efficient living (low carbon or carbon neutral), affordable and sustainable eco-housing program (through sharing centralized facilities, such as large kitchen, utility room, central garden, as well as having the option of car-sharing) and income generation within the co-housing community (e.g. childcare, community services). This practice has promoted a behavioural change towards reducing energy consumption through a change in purchasing patterns and a modification in daily habits.

4.1.2 Alternative Marketplace: ITC e-Choupal^{81, 82} in Bihar, India

Case: The local farmer community of Bihar in India experienced a lack of market accessibility due to information inconsistency. This required the need of employing middlemen to operate technological platforms. The farmers had little negotiating power over the selling prices of their crops due to the government-mandated marketplace (called *mandi*⁸⁴)⁸⁵.

Method: The ITC rural agribusiness conglomerate provided internet access and market pricing information, which could thereafter boost the local farmer economy. The middlemen were eliminated and the e-Choupal was established as a new pricing and negotiating technological information gateway.

Source⁸³

⁷⁷ Ibid ²⁸

⁷⁸ <http://www.sustainable-lifestyles.eu>

⁷⁹ <http://cohousing.org.uk/groups>

⁸⁰ Ibid ⁸⁰

⁸¹ Ibid ³

⁸² <http://www.itcportal.com/businesses/agri-business/e-choupal.aspx>

⁸³ Ibid ³

⁸⁴ Kuttayan, A. & Rao, S. (2003), What Works: ITC's e-Choupal and Profitable Rural Transformation. World Resources Institute, University of Michigan, University of North Carolina

⁸⁵ Ibid ³

Practice (Best or Good): This is an alternative marketplace model, which is used in order to strengthen the agribusiness supply chain as well as its relations to the local farmer community. The success of this model has led to 40% agribusiness revenue increase due to e-Choupal, increased growth and offers the farmers a new power, which is that of being able to influence the *mandi* system⁸⁶.

4.2 Participatory methods and tools

Apart from practical methods for implementing renewable energy project, such as by the use of wind turbines (in the Danish Samsø island), community energy initiatives rely also on a number of other technological methods to attract quick and effective social responses. These methods empower people to take action and relate to applications of social media, social gaming, the involvement of citizens in science and communication through online platforms.

SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media offer **important facilitators and virtual hubs** for information, communication between stakeholders, social engagement, entrepreneurship and social innovation in community energy within and across borders or geographies.

UK “City Air” App

In the city of London, more than 3,000 people every year, experience health problems due to the high levels of air pollution (toxic air). Killer air particles (PM2.5 toxic particles), affect public health and people’s lives. This concern gave rise to the development of the UK “City Air” application⁸⁸ which is part of a virtual hub called i-genius⁸⁹ (promoting social entrepreneurship across 200 countries). This application offers live alerts of the “city air” toxicity, according to the area of navigation and given route.

CleaNap

During the last 2 decades Naples suffers from a severe waste management problem. The crisis outburst in 2008 due to increased municipal solid wastes overflowing the landfills. To date, this problem remains unresolved. CleaNap⁹¹ is a social media tool that was invented for this purpose. It empowered citizens to address waste issues across their community in Napoli and helped towards the development of a community group that came together and cleaned up the city’s square.

⁸⁶ Ibid ³

⁸⁷ <http://cityairapp.com>

⁸⁸ Ibid ⁸⁸

⁸⁹ www.i-genius.org

⁹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Naples_waste_management_issue#/media/File:Napoli_2010-by-RaBoe-40.jpg

⁹¹ Ibid ²⁸

SOCIAL GAMING

Online social gaming can **educate people** on environmental issues, such as waste management, conservation of biodiversity and the mitigation of natural disaster.

Source⁹²

BBC Climate Change⁹³, focusing on sustainable development and policies over the last century (≈110 years)

CITIZENS INVOLVEMENT IN SCIENCE

Source⁹⁴

Developing an Eco-Museum in a Swedish Kristianstads-Vattenrike Biosphere Reserve by citizens' involvement in monitoring wildlife living within the wetland. This is a good example of **incorporating the citizens' involvement in understanding and preserving the ecosystem**. A benefit of this practice has been that members of the public were recruited to help monitor wildlife in the area. This project was nationally driven, as its aim was to inform national and related wider European initiatives. Logistics support came from local Universities including the Kristianstad University.

COMMUNICATION

Communications between citizens and/or communities that face common problems across different geographies

Source⁹⁵

Green Plant Protection in Slovakia⁹⁶, enabling farmers and the general public to inform themselves on plant pesticides, pathogens and more in order to reduce their use and promote a more ecological agriculture.

⁹² <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/resources/idt-5aceb360-8bc3-4741-99f0-2e4f76ca02bb>

⁹³ http://www.bbc.co.uk/sn/hottopics/climatechange/climate_challenge/aboutgame.shtml

⁹⁴ Ibid ³

⁹⁵ http://www.adam-europe.eu/pri/5939/prd/4/2/Book-jacket_GPP_ENsk.pdf

⁹⁶ <http://www.greenplantprotection.eu>

5. Success and Failure factors

Social innovations applied in community energy projects rely on a variety of positive and negative factors that may influence or detriment their successful implementation. A particularly successful European biomass project, providing heating alternatives, is the REGBIE+ (Regional Initiatives Increasing the Market for Biomass Heating in Europe, 2007)⁹⁷. This project involves 13 partners from 11 EU countries and focuses in inspiring innovative biomass energy solutions across Europe. An example of such work is the Jühnde, Germany bioenergy village presented above (in Community Energy Section).

Motivation Mix: Important Preconditions for the Success of a Project

Based on the analysis of qualitative research on the German Jühnde project, it has been identified that *important preconditions*⁹⁸ for the beginning of a social innovation community energy projects relate to the **motivation mix of the community**. This means that there is wide variety of motives that lead a community in succeeding towards a new incentive scheme. These are effectively three and target **environmental and ecological motives** (related to eco-friendly, sensible uses of natural resources), **social and anthropocentric motives** as well as **economic motives**. Interestingly, although the environmental motives should be considered as more important (given the environmental value of using renewable energy sources), it is necessary to acknowledge that the economic motives appeared to be stronger. In the Jühnde project for example, the economic motives related to the potential of bioenergy independence of the community and consequently the potential of a reduction of individuals' and the community's energy bills.

Active Involvement of a Variety of Stakeholders – A key success factor

Another important factor towards the success of this project was that its initiators were trusted as they were generally acknowledged as “well-known” community members. The specific practice that empowered the success of this project was the **combination of support from a large variety of stakeholders such as, municipalities, local councils, authorities, district administrations, the mayor cooperatives, renewable energy organizations** (e.g. the German Biogas Association), **planning offices, funding bodies and individuals'** (e.g. inhabitants who engaged actively). The methods that supported the development of this project were based predominantly on local networking and face-to-face communications where the reasons for the implementation of the project (stating the common good) were addressed. Additionally, information was offered transparently (through communication) to the community members who thereafter showed trust in the bioenergy project. This information included data on the local financial and economic benefits of the alternative energy project implementation. The best practices however related also to a softer social engagement in this project through local events (e.g. on topics of alternative energy production, use, benefits) and presentations of local core competencies (e.g. for farming, construction works) in related to the cost benefits from using alternative energy sources (as compared to the use of, e.g. fossil fuels).

Policy Framework and Public Acceptance

The Jühnde community projects generally received suitable finances for its implementation and its success increased publicity, attracted local stakeholders' interest and received further economic benefits. Through this project, new jobs were created; local politicians paid visits to their community and received sponsorship awards. As a consequence of the project success, **the community had the opportunity to connect with biogas experts**. Through this venture, they were able to bond and take pride of their community energy achievement and more importantly gained confidence in taking actions to improve their own lifestyles. Further to the successful completion of the Jühnde social innovation community energy projects, new targets and goals were discussed⁹⁹ for the expansion of the existing and the implementation of new complementary projects.

Obstacles: Impeding Factors

⁹⁷ http://www.regbieplus.eu/fileadmin/files/Success_Stories/REGBIE_Success_Stories_01.pdf

⁹⁸ <http://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/4/2/244/htm>

⁹⁹ Ibid ⁹⁹

Further to interviews carried out to Jühnde stakeholders, *impeding factors* for the successful implementation¹⁰⁰ of this community energy projects were identified to be to **the lack of effective support from intermediaries, a relative paucity of support from policymakers¹⁰¹ and the lack of understanding from the policy sector** (who usually understand social innovations as a “one-size-fits-all” procedure¹⁰²). A lack of: local acceptance for change, awareness of environmental issues (in connection to the specific location of interest), skills and resources, mutual support (issues of policy-making, place, practice, product, relating to the industries, intermediaries, individuals) and clarity in addressing the community responsibility could have detrimental effects to the successful implementation of social innovation community energy projects.

Additionally, financial uncertainty, lack of assurance¹⁰³, conflict of economic interests (e.g. between former fossil oil suppliers and potential biomass providers¹⁰⁴), disinformation or negative propaganda were suggested, through the interviews, to increase doubts amongst the community. That is regarding the cost efficiency of the plan, the security of the energy supply, the smell and noise as well as finally the potential risk of accidents.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid 28

¹⁰¹ Ibid 99

¹⁰² Ibid 28

¹⁰³ Ibid 99

¹⁰⁴ Ibid 99

6. Interviews in the field

6.1 Key findings and Observations

Having identified through the literature review various success and failure factors for social innovation applied to community energy projects, ISABEL has further conducted 18 semi-structured interviews of a range of stakeholders (presented in the following table). The interviewee sample was a convenience sample of participants in existing projects and thus, inevitably, they are able to speak more to successful than unsuccessful projects and they likely have had less exposure to obstacles to the success of their projects. The main interview questions addressed are presented in Appendix 3 and key findings of the interviews are presented in the following sections 6.1.1 to 6.1.18. The interviews have focused on identifying answers to the questions: *What were the key success factors? What obstacles were overcome? How? Participants were also asked to specify the type of renewable energy and community energy model.*

List of Interviews carried out by ISABEL partners

	Partner	Interviewer	Date	Initiative	Interviewee	Position	Region	Country	Classification of Industry
1	EBW	Anna Fragkidou	18/03/2016	Cluster of Bioenergy & Environment of Western Macedonia (CluBE)	Ntavos Nikos	Manager of CluBE	Westren Macedonia (North Greece)	Greece	bioenergy and environment, green economy
2	EBW	Anna Fragkidou	16/03/2016	Energy Cooperative Company in Karditsa Prefecture	Bellis Vasilis	General Director of Development Agency of Karditsa	Prefecture of Karditsa (region opf Thessaly, middle Greece)	Greece	production of pellet from agricultural and forest biomass waste
3	FNR	Diego Piedra Garcia	14/03/2016	Bioenergy village Bollewick		Feasibility analyzer	Bollewick (North-East Germany)	Germany	biogas CHP
4	GBTF	Andrew Ormerod	21/02/2016	Methanogen UK Ltd	Angie Bywater	Publicity, marketing and construction of biogas equipment		UK	
5	GBTF	Andrew Ormerod	21/03/2016	Community energy solutions	Colin Risbridger		Orkney Islands (North Scotland)	UK	Heart and Power
6	GBTF	Andrew Ormerod	14/03/2016	Camphill Community	Mark Dwan		Ballytobin County Kilkenny	Ireland	Biogas project with combined heat and power and district grid
7	GBTF	Andrew Ormerod	16/03/2016	Malaby Biogas	Thomas Minter		Warminster Wilts (South-West England)	UK	Smaller scale private biogas plant dealing with food waste
8	GBTF	Andrew Ormerod	21/03/2016	Devon Community Composting Network	Nicky Scott		Devon (South-West England)	UK	Community Composting
9	GBTF	Andrew Ormerod	21/03/2016	Lymm Community Energy	Richard Pearce		Cheshire (North West England)	UK	Community energy (PV)
10	LCF	Antje Foell	23/03/2016	Municipal Energy Supplier Radolfzell	Stefanie Hambalek	Project Engineer		Germany	Heating systems
11	LCF	Antje Foell	24/03/2016	District heating network Voellkofen GmbH	Martin Hafner	Farmer / Owner of agricultural biogas plant		Germany	Agricultural biogas plant
12	LCF	Antje Foell	23/03/2016	Solarcomplex AG Supply Chain Bioenergy	Hanspeter Walz	Project Manager		Germany	Supply chain bioenergy

	Partner	Interviewer	Date	Initiative	Interviewee	Position	Region	Country	Classification of Industry
13	Q-PLAN	Manthos Bougiouklis	16/03/2016	Laconic Bioenergy SA	Argyropoulos Stavros		Prefecture of Laconia (region of Peloponnese, South Greece)	Greece	collection, disposal and management of urban waste (recycling, biogas/electricity, fertiliser)
14	Q-PLAN	Manthos Bougiouklis	16/03/2016	Spirit of Lanarkshire - Wind Energy Cooperative Ltd	Helen Grayshan		Lanarkshire County, Scotland	UK	local wind park
15	WR	Yorgos Chalkias	17/03/2016	ZEZ Cooperative	Edo Jerkic	Manager		Croatia	Cooperative of energy experts that functions as a know-how platform
16	WR	Yorgos Chalkias	22/03/2016	Hashoej Biogas Cooperative	Frederik Madsen	Manager	Region Hovedstaden - island of Zealand (Eastern Denmark)	Denmark	Biogas cooperative
17	WR	Yorgos Chalkias	18/03/2016	SVEF cooperative	Hans Björkström	President of the board of directors		Sweden	Wind power cooperative
18	SURREY	Davide Poggio	16/03/2016	Sharenergy is a co-op	Jon Halle	Member of Sharenergy		UK	Wind, PV, Biomass and Hydro

6.1.1 The Bioenergy & Environment Cluster of Western Macedonia (Clu.B.E.) - Greece

Clu.B.E. is a Greek Non-Profit company.

Practice

Clu.B.E. cover a range of **partnerships** from the public sector, academia and institutions to entrepreneurs (such as Biogas plant services).

Success Factors

This bioenergy and environment cluster is **self-funded and community managed** (financially independent).

Obstacles & Failure Factors

Communication Obstacles

- Convincing all relevant stakeholders in the region for the necessity of establishing the cluster, its credibility and benefits for themselves as well as for the whole region in general for supporting it
- Persuading competitive enterprises to work together in joint actions
- Persuading enterprises in general to cooperate with the public sector

Implications for Biogas

There is strong interest in the region for the establishment of biogas plants. Companies who breed fur-bearing animals are interested in biogas production. As there are serious problems in the supply chain due to the seasonality of the raw material (there are time periods of 200.000 animals and of 2.000.000 animals), they are trying to secure biomass quantities from other sources.

6.1.2 Energy Cooperative Company in Karditsa Prefecture (ECCK) - Greece

This is a **partnership** between all residents of this prefecture.

Practice

Up to 2016, it has 360 members that own 393 shares in total. Out of the 360 members, 33 own a farm, while 23 are farmers mainly. Each share costs 1.000 € and one member can hold up to 6 shares, still having only one vote (one vote/member). The capital was deposited at the Cooperative Bank of Karditsa.

Success Factors

ECCK has as a **role model** (similar to a cooperative initiative) to the “co-operative bank of Karditsa” representing high **profitability**. ECCK, in this way, has gained the **trust of the local communities**.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- Breaking the existing circle of the **supply chain** and **operational method** (mainly of agricultural biomass projects) acted as an important obstacle as the farmers were reluctant to participate. There was a general **lack of trust in the technical standards** followed for the construction of the plant and thus were requesting for guaranteed quantities assurance of the new plant program.
- **Environmental legislation for project and licensing**. Initially the biomass power plant was licensed for erection and operation in a specific purchased land while the pellet plant was not. This led to a 15-months delay in the project in order to convince the relevant authorities that licensing should follow the same rules as before.

Implications for Biogas

ECCK's future plan is to build a new technologically advanced biomass power plant. It would also like to exploit new methods to generate thermal energy. Exploiting the livestock waste for producing biogas is an additional aim of ECCK, which would also aim for the development of a new biomass supply chain.

6.1.3 Bioenergy village Bollewick - Germany

This interview was addressed to a member of the project planning company.

Practice

The project Bollewick is a Public-Private-Partnership with a cooperative investment concept. The project partners are the municipality Bollewick/Kambs, the ARGE Bioenergie Bollewick GbR, and the Consortium DorfKERN.

The village Bollewick uses the CHP concept to supply heat for space heating and domestic hot water. The AD is operated by two farmers and the heat grid is operated by the municipality.

The village Kambs has a similar concept but here a farmer is operating the biogas plant and the heat grid, important for this sub-project is that the end users are regional industry companies: joinery and timber yard. Here the change value is the wood process.

Moreover, that the Bollewick' residents benefit from heating with renewable energy resources, the heating prices are less than the normal price for fuel oil.

100% the construction services were made by companies from federal state Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania. i.e. only regional companies were part of the construction. The idea behind this concept is that the supply chain should be in the region.

Success Factors

- **Communication & Transparency** - The communication is the best way to deal with obstacles. All the process must be comprehensible for all stakeholders, during the planning can happen that the first ideas aren't feasible. The group has to be flexible enough to go new ways to find new solution, but for the people have to be clear that they are entrepreneurs with all the risks.
- **Biomass feedstock** - planning: amount of guarantee biomass for a long period
- **Competitive capacity** - price comparison to oil, gas

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- **Political and legal frameworks** (before the "Energie Wende" and the EEG (German RES-act) the energy community projects were small cooperatives)
- **Lack of acceptance** of the stakeholders the new incentive's economic risks: Mental barriers
- Project **feasibility** analysis (region may not have enough biomass)
- Planning and **budgeting** (project implementation is too expensive for the region)

Implications for Biogas

CHP and biogas are inseparable in the community energy concept.

Energy conversion efficiency and the energy efficient must be the future priority e.g. smart villages. Biogas projects have one important advantage: the storage facilities e.g. photovoltaic electricity is only available, if you have sunshine.

6.1.4 Methanogen UK Ltd - UK

This company is undertaking publicity and marketing and construction of composting and **biogas** equipment.

Practice

This involves the **cooperation** between **academia**, specifically the BBSRC NIBB Anaerobic Digestion Network at University of Southampton, and an **Industrial Biotechnology and Bioenergy Network**. As part of their role they can provide £10,000 business opportunity - match funding from the businesses can be in cash or kind to employ an academic to test proof of concepts and there are good links

between the different NIBB thematic groups. Resolving problems and overcoming obstacles is achieved by following successful community energy **role models** (e.g. UK taking that of Denmark).

Success Factors

Optimum solution for a sustainable energy community is a **mix of renewables** (solar/wind/wood chip/biogas with CHP for example) depending on planning constraints. As mentioned island communities are potentially good examples to demonstrate local resilience, however this hasn't proved easy. In the Isle of White the 'Eco island project' it was aimed at using 100% renewables from a range of energy solutions, such as to generate biogas from the local zoo.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

The UK local **authority** food waste is nowadays tied up on long contracts that can't be broken – which involve long lorry journeys – this overlooks possibilities of an array of very small AD plants dealing with local food waste – particularly in cities – because of shortage of feed stock some attempts to establish these have resulted in a few AD facilities established running half empty. **Lack of support** for transport of local feedstock through a national park was part of the reason that Sustainable Youlgrave's AD plant (planned as community digester linked to a farm digester) **didn't get planning permission** in the Derbyshire Peak District. **Legal constraints, lack of understanding of the technology** and **red tape act** as major obstacles which can defeat even the most determined with well researched sound projects.

The situation in Scotland appears to be different and even harder than England in terms of '**red tape**' over AD and biogas production. Biogas production could be ideal for island communities rather than carrying waste to the mainland. The clash between the Quality Meat Scotland and Zero Waste Scotland has been on-going for quite a while – the former restricted application of AD treated slurry to grassland killing off the biogas projects in Orkney. There have been quality standards tested and introduced and gradually official attitudes are changing in relation to the safety of the treated slurry. There appears to be tight restrictions on AD plants in Scotland and even small-scale digesters down to the size of a teacup require a £1500 license fee.

Implications for Biogas

Solar followed by wind have predominated in private or community energy projects in the UK as they are much simpler to achieve compared to biogas and hydro from funding. Really the easier option is on-farm composting. The interviewee suggested placing a small-scale community digester next to a farm scale digester, very much like the model in Denmark. This makes pasteurizing the food waste that much easier and the pasteurized digestate is then fed into the farm scale digester – the higher nutrient value of the food waste increases the biogas yield from the system.

6.1.5 Community Energy Solutions in Orkney – Scotland, UK

Formerly involved with community biogas but this failed due to external influences

Practice

This is a Heat and Power renewable energy projects in Westray (one of the outlying islands in Orkney). As part of this project, it was attempted to introduce **social innovation** by trying to implement the concept of a **nutrient bank within the community**. This involved a biogas plant and digestate store where members of the community could deposit organic materials and then remove those nutrients at a different time of year in the form of digestate. Biogas can provide for a number of farmers and the local authority in terms of handling and harnessing organic materials. The ability to digest animal slurry also reduces the smell associated with the spreading to land of these materials, which is beneficial to the wider community. These are social benefits through **co-operation and collaboration**.

Their **community is defined by the geographical boundary** of the island and community energy projects are projects, which are **owned by resident members**, or organizations with their head office

on the island. The purpose of the nutrient bank concept was to reduce the emissions to their environment.

Success Factors

They have a 900kW community wind turbine on the island, which was successful, and the social innovation initiative, which began from this, included the organization Community Power Orkney, which went on to support other communities. **Wind energy** has been much more successful as it is easier to implement and much **more familiar for funding bodies**. Also the **incentives were higher for wind energy than biogas**.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

They were ultimately unsuccessful with the social innovation as the **rules imposed** by Quality Meat Scotland prevented digestate from anything other than on farm wastes being spread on that farm. This made it too difficult for digestate to be used on farms other than the one, which hosted the biogas plant. As a result there are no biogas facilities operating in the vicinity. Communities can undertake the social innovation required solving their own problems but unfortunately it is **policy makers** remote from that community who will ultimately decide whether it will be successful. Policies are too often developed with **one-size fits all approach** and these seldom benefit the remote peripheral areas such as this community.

The potential is always there with an intensive agricultural community however the **policy and legislative barriers** at the moment prevent the widespread adoption of this technology. A general strategy on community energy would not be specific enough for biogas. Indeed Orkney is now working with the Scottish Government on island proofing legislation to minimize these problems. You need to identify early on the benefits that your project will bring and focus on these rather than designing the project to suit any particular policy requirement. Biogas can **solve environmental, energy and waste treatment problems** but it is hard to balance all of these benefits and still deliver something economically viable.

Implications for Biogas

It should be compulsory for the electricity network operators to connect community energy projects with a cap on the cost of doing so. The charges should be socialized across all energy users. As for biogas at Community Energy level is currently just too expensive at the scale required. One anomaly is that you can heat the digester from wind energy and gain energy bonus payments from Feed in Tariffs (FiTs) but you are not allowed to heat the digester using biogas and claim the Renewable Heat Incentive (RHI) bonus. The interviewee said that 'Given my time again I would not have built a biogas plant as it was unsuccessful economically'. With the ending of Feed in tariffs their emphasis will shift to energy efficiency projects and shared savings.

6.1.6 Camphill Community Biogas Project at Ballytobin County Kilkenny in Ireland – Ireland

Biogas project with combined heat and power and district grid linking different buildings for a community catering for 75 people with special needs and their co-workers, providing residential needs in 6 shared homes as well as education and work on a farm. They also have wood chip heating for outlying buildings.

Practice

This is and has been, from the start, an entirely **community-owned and community-driven scheme**. It is the first community led and only biogas micro grid system in Ireland. They have just added a CHP unit to the system so they expect to meet all their heat and power needs entirely from renewable energy sources. There are two outlying houses (2km away from the central micro grid of the community and so not possible to link) which each has PV solar and wood pellet systems. The system has been up and running since 1998 which over time they have expanded and added new components. It has provided heat successfully to the community for the past 15 years.

The ethos of the community is to provide a **collaborative social foundation** – you get further by helping each other. “Ways of creating our own energy and collaborative ways of creating our own economy our own food production these come quite easily once you have established a social foundation of mutual support.” They aim to be **self-sufficient and ecologically sustainable** for their food and energy needs. They produce 80% of their own food and this provides **work opportunities**. The self-sufficiency in energy is part of a miniature ecosystem 100% of heat is provided by biogas and initially electricity is 70% but we hope that this will go up to 100%. **Savings in energy** allow money to circulate in the community and provide comfort for resident.

Success Factors

The **commercial waste processing** aspect has also been good for the community. Feed stock includes farmers slurry and food waste. This was lucrative in the early years when they were the only facility of this nature in Ireland. Competition has increased now and there are more costly restrictions and regulations to adhere to now. Even so any **surplus or profit has always been re-directed to the community as capital for projects** needed by the community. The **neighbouring farmers financially benefitted from the system** in terms of improved nutrient quality and quantity.

The interviewee and one of his colleagues have more recently set up another company called "ecobeo" to further develop **biogas and synergetic energy systems and enterprises**. An example is growing willow plantations that thrive on digestate. The willows then get harvested and made into wood chip to supply gasification CHP units. So **further energy benefits** can happen down the chain. The wood chips can be transported to where energy is needed in locations not suited for biogas. Adoption fitted into requirement to limit methane emissions larger scale adoption would limit greenhouse gas production in Ireland.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

When the biogas plant was built in 1998 there was no grant aid in Ireland unlike the high levels at the time in Germany and Denmark at that time 30-40% and they had a good price for green electricity and low interest loans. The cost and capital for setting up the new enterprise was the biggest barriers in Ireland.

Implications for Biogas

The biogas and CHP facility at Camphill at Ballytobin hasn't been replicated at other Camphill Communities in the UK according to Mark Dwan. He is involved in other biogas projects in Ireland and is aware from past experience about the sensitivity of bigger communities such as towns and villages and the need when planning **to get local people to be involved in ownership of the scheme**.

6.1.7 Malaby Biogas Plant – England, UK

Smaller scale private biogas plant dealing with food waste

Practice

Malaby biogas is a private company that was designed and built by Thomas Minters company themselves. They only process food waste. Food waste from different sources requires different designs and management systems. There are different categories of material, **from local authorities, businesses, pubs and restaurants**. With **local authority, community or private firms** there are different models of business. With local authority food waste there is competitive tendering, this could be tendering against other AD organizations or in vessel composting or incineration companies. Local authority food waste can be complicated, takes a long time and is risky. Malaby operates merchant or open gate processing for food waste on shorter length contracts such as for a year.

There is a range of reasons for this including **long-term contracts** between **local authorities and larger waste contract companies** and AD or in vessel composting or incinerator companies that cannot be altered. There are some smaller private companies who have successfully bid for contracts though.

Success Factors

Not clearly stated.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

One of the problems is that there are **declining income from the gas or electricity** in the UK in terms of the Feed in Tariffs and Renewable Heat Incentives. Feed stock gate fees are declining and this is quite a competitive situation. Companies bid down the feed stock price and in some cases they pay for it. The government is decreasing funding. The interviewee thought there would be very few small communities based AD systems that can process food waste – although there may be some very small examples.

Implications for Biogas

As far as any community project he suggested identifying what feedstock and how to procure it will take a year to plan. You have to allow for a **decrease in feed in tariff** over the year. If you are considering producing biogas for the gas grid for RHI revenue for injecting into the grid, select site near a gas grid. He considered problem with smaller scale community schemes is that they would have a **problem sourcing enough local food waste** for a community based waste system.

6.1.8 Devon Community Composting Network – England, UK

Devon Community Composting Network predates the UK Community Composting Network, with which the interviewee has close ties. He undertakes work for Devon Council on community composting.

Practice

Devon's community composting network is founded on a **circular economy** and including a **'high value' use for the composted material**- such as horticulture and food production – what would be better would be nursery plant raising or other high value activities. With his other hat on he has a 'Proper job' which includes composting, horticulture and a café. He is involved with **composting linked to education in schools**.

Success Factors

There are some very interesting reasons why Devon Community Composting Network has survived so long. They charge for what they do and they encourage youngsters into **jobs and careers** through what they do and they have a long successful track record in this.

The interviewee has renewed interest to learn more about the application of micro AD and biogas generation, influenced by the success of Rockier Yaman in London (**role model**) and the fact that **the technology for small scale AD is now more robust**. He is interested in following up his successful school composting program in Devon with school based biogas and has the ear of **policy-makers** in Devon County Council. He has indicated the need to **link it to a tangible outcome, food and health, which is important on the schools curriculum**.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

In common with other interviewees involved in small scale composting and AD involving food waste there are complaints about the way the **law** has changed, which has lead to local **authorities signing up long-term contracts** with councils for the removal of food waste that cannot be legally broken to allow feed stock for small scale operations. Devon is a very progressive region of the UK in terms of community energy projects.

Lack of awareness: Fear that composting is smelly.

In terms of the **circular economy** there can be problems when certain segments of the whole do **not mesh into the whole**, for example, where the veg. growers on his land are not using the compost and where schools don't quite get the importance of community composting alongside their solar and PV

and decide to drop it. Or where a new head comes in and asks him to remove his smelly composting without understanding its role.

Implications for Biogas

As far as community biogas there was an attempt by Otter Rotter's a composting outfit in East Devon to establish a small scale AD plant in a poly tunnel a few years ago – under the Alchemy project unfortunately this didn't work because of **technical issues** including too infrequent addition of food waste to the digester.

6.1.9 Lymm Community Energy in Cheshire – England, UK

Community energy (PV) encouraging the improvement of private and public buildings

Practice

Low Carbon Lymm set it up in 2015 in **collaboration** with Warrington **Borough Council** as a **Community Benefit Society** with the **Financial Conduct Authority**. Its innovation is financial - enable local people and organizations to invest in renewable energy installations that benefit the local community. They have some sophisticated approaches in terms of **community engagement and networking** to share information with other bodies, which are worth noting for any community biogas projects. They form a network of community energy in the region including **local authorities** and **energy companies** and **share best practice information to encourage each other**.

Success Factors

They are also involved in low energy lighting using new financing mechanisms to deliver social benefits. Occupants of the buildings will get **lower cost energy**, whilst the **investors** will get a **return on their investment** – and any surplus will fund community energy efficiency projects. It is involved with schemes to fit solar panels to **public buildings** such as **schools** and **community halls** – this not only helps their **budgets stretch** further to **cover their core activities – education and community activities** it also brings the community together in relation to helping to install the panels.

On the community level, they reach out to private dwellings and public buildings **Surplus profits from energy generation** are used to encourage up take of low energy lighting; replacement boilers and preventing energy leakage in older buildings. To get the community on board it is worth showing how householders can benefit by working with them and householder to householder exchange of views is more likely to be effective than a hard sell. To this end they have established a **Green Trail** so people can see what others have done and arrange visits to their houses. This is similar to the **Green Open Home approach** organized by the **Centre for Sustainable Energy in Bristol (intermediary)**.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

They have had a target of installing 50-100 kW a year over a five-year period energy saving initiatives. However, this is likely to be affected by UK government **funding to support sustainable energy projects which is now much reduced**. There is a lot of unrealized potential for community energy projects. Because the **government** has **cut** feed in **tariffs** and **tax relief** in relation to investment has been removed (it was 50% tax relief up to £150 000 was 'Seed Enterprise Scheme' and 30% tax relief for 'Enterprise Schemes'). They are looking at other ways of projects off the ground European low carbon initiative funding and 'Power of Change' government funding. One of the main obstacles is the **high 'up front' 'costs** to get projects off the ground, to **pay for local energy network and structural surveys**. These are **expensive** for an organization run by volunteers.

Implications for Biogas

Having a sophisticated approach in terms of **community engagement and networking** to share information with other bodies, which are worth noting for any community biogas projects.

6.1.10 Municipal Energy Supplier Radolfzell (SWR) – Germany

SWR (Stadtwerke Radolfzell) is the municipal energy supplier in the city of Radolfzell, which has established one district-heating network.

Practice

SWR (Stadtwerke Radolfzell) is based on biomass (biogas and woodchips, including a solar power plant on the central heating station) and is planning a second district-heating network, based on solar heat and biomass.

Success Factors

- **Successful** projects in the **past**
- **Regular information**
- **Financial participation** in the project: secure yield over ten years
- **Financial “sweeteners”**: possibility to buy a part of the solar power plant on the central heating station and receive money
- **Reliability** and **professionalism** of the municipal energy supplier

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- **Choice of location**: high prices for sites= find a ground owner who is not looking only for money, but supports renewable energy
 - Sites near to living areas= inform people about technical facts (noise, dust, delivery), show visual concepts
 - Sites in nature conservation areas= find solutions with local and regional authorities, everyone should focus on how to realize the project)
- **Price** for heat should be the same in the projects

Implications for Biogas

- **Bioenergy**: People appreciate to use their private biomass in their **local heating network**, but realization is difficult because of **technical issues**
- **Evaluation**: Information event every year, presenting current state, new **techniques**, explain changing **prices**, discuss everything what is important for the involved people

6.1.11 District Heating Network Völkofen GmbH - Germany

M. Hafner built the biogas plant in 2004 and established the district-heating network in 2012/13 in Germany.

Practice

The district heating network in Völkofen GmbH has been initiated by M. Hafner (own-initiative).

Success Factors

- **Support** from renewable energy stakeholders and other initiatives
- Citizens’ **willingness** to use renewable energy
- Work of **convincing**

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- Missing initiative of the **municipal authorities**
- **Financial risk**: Very big for one person
- Missing knowledge in credit institutes regarding **financial support** of district heating networks
- **Missing willingness** of citizens to be part of the district-heating network (*e.g.* they just installed a new heating system, they are very critical regarding the costs)
- **Missing support to establish a cooperative**
- **Preparatory effort**: Financial, planning
- **Structure of the village**: ‘Straßendörfer’, means long roads with only one house at the side
- **Political framework**: End of financial support of RE, especially bioenergy
- **Evaluation**: No, technique is established and works well

Implications for Biogas

Future scenario: Financial **support** for biogas ends after 20years (in this case in 2024), until know its unsecure how biogas plants will be supported/survive after this period. Mr. Hafner will keep the district-heating network, if it's not possible anymore with biogas, he will change to wood chips.

6.1.12 Solarcomplex AG Supply Chain Bioenergy – Germany

Solarcomplex AG is a citizen company founded in 2000. In 2016 there are about 1500 people involved financially.

Practice

Solarcomplex AG includes bioenergy (bioenergy villages – district heating network), solar power, water-power and wind power in their portfolio.

Success Factors

- One person as **driving force**
- **Cost effectiveness** as well as good presentation of this
- Best practice examples from further projects/activities
- **Regional company** (authentic)

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- **Conflicts** at local level (e.g. citizens' initiative against solar park in their environment)
- **Lack of willingness** of people to be part of the heating network based on renewable energy: **Competition** with oil price, competition with gas price isn't possible), some people just installed new heating systems in their houses
- Choice of location for renewable energy plant: **Statutory requirements**
- **Political framework:** Change/end of supporting renewable energy, lobbying is necessary
- **Not every project reached realization in the last years

Implications for Biogas

- **Financial controlling**
- **Technical** development
- Take into account for **new projects**

6.1.13 Laconic Bioenergy SA - Greece

The main concept: every house, entrepreneur, factory or place with human activity produce not 'waste' but 'useful products-materials' which can be reused as raw materials or source of energy.

Practice

Laconic Bioenergy SA is a "Grassroots" company was initiated by **30 Laconic entrepreneurs** in September 2011, to confront the problem of collection, disposal and management of urban **waste of the municipality of Sparta** (capital of Laconia) with a **positive environmental and socio-economic impact**. The main idea is that **waste is 'sorted at the source'** separating organic matter, paper, glass, metal, plastic, wood, vegetable oil, etc. with a view to reuse them as raw materials (recycling), while household organic matter and biomass will be used for the production of biogas (and eventually of electricity and heat), and fertiliser.

Success Factors

- **Benefits for its shareholders:** a) possible annual return depending on **profits**, b) creation of **jobs** and c) **reinvestment to the local economy**.
- **Good knowledge of the legislation and the European community model experience**

- **The choice of the most productive and transparent legal form** - According to the interviewee, former efforts of **farm cooperatives** had no capacity to succeed due to a) the **lack of cooperative culture and tradition** (in comparison to countries like Germany); b) the involvement of **political parties** in their operation; and c) the fact that each member had the same voting rights regardless of its financial contribution. As a result, the interest and the active participation of their members faded over time. On the contrary, the statute of the Laconic Bioenergy SA enhances the **active participation** of their members, while participation is open to anyone (preferably to local individuals) who has real interest in its mission and depend their vote and influence on the numbers of shares they hold.
- **Local authorities collaboration** - Without the collaboration of **local authorities** in the implementation and monitoring of the initiative, its aims cannot easily be achieved
- **Communication activities** - Communication activities play a crucial role to the promotion of the aim and vision of the initiative **enhancing the public acceptance** in terms of positive perception and active participation.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- **Difficulties of Community Energy RES initiatives to compete with the major private investments / lack of adequate energy infrastructure** - Even though the regulation is not against to community energy initiatives (which are typically small to medium size and have a regional orientation) they face difficulties to overcome **bureaucratic issues** compared to the major private investments in their effort to obtain the right of connection to the electrical grid. Moreover, the lack of adequate energy infrastructure in terms of a low number of connection points hinders further the regional – oriented initiatives’ effort.
- **Inability of the public authorities to properly support CE RES initiatives** - In many cases due to structural and organisational reasons the local authorities fail to properly support such initiatives. Laconic SA in that case tackled this problem though intensive effort to establish personal contacts with the authorities.
- **Preconceptions in local community** - There are individuals who are reluctant to join initiatives as they could be considered as ‘extremely progressive’. Positive communication activities can alter partially this way of thinking.
- **Lack of measuring and monitoring renewable energy capacity** - That obstacle can be talked by the step-by-step development of planning.
- **Lack of experienced organizations in supporting community initiatives in terms of business, finance and operation** - Laconic SA, dealt with this problem using the business experience and efforts of its initial members who were active entrepreneurs in the region.
- **Lack of financial support** - The economic crisis and existing **legislation** exclude similar initiatives from additional financing (loans, subsidies).
- **Traditionally negative perception in such efforts** - The conservative way of thinking is overcome by continued communicative efforts.

Implications for Biogas

- To increase the engagement of citizens in the company’s shareholder scheme and establish an integrated model of household waste management by:
- Setting up a **biogas plant utilising household organic matter** as well as agricultural and livestock residues in order to produce electricity and fertilizer
- Promoting the **concept of gathering vegetable oil** (for the production of biodiesel) from schools, which the company will purchase to support the schools’ heating problem
- Setting up **sanitary waste landfill**, where the limited residue is going to be disposed

6.1.14 Spirit of Lanarkshire Wind Energy Cooperative Ltd – Scotland, UK

Spirit of Lanarkshire Wind Energy Cooperative Ltd was established in 2013, as a **Co-operative Society** by **Energy4All**, a non-profit social enterprise (co-operative) with best business practices. Energy4All, after an innovative agreement with commercial developer **Falk Renewables Wind Ltd**, offered the opportunity to local energy co-operative **Spirit of Lanarkshire**, to hold an economic stake in two of the Falk's local Wind Park developments. *The Wind Park sites operate properly since 2014.*

Practice

The most effective community energy practices are Wind Farm and Hydro electrical installation due to the vast capacity of wind and hydro energy in Scotland (weather conditions). Smaller community organisations (**charities, multi community organisations**) are doing **low budget projects** to insulate community centres and village halls. The Scottish **government** supports the public sector (public scheme no community scheme) to insulate home (energy poverty). **Legislation** demands from new buildings to meet high standards of energy efficiency. For older building the Energy Saving Trust (branch of the government) promotes domestic and business energy efficiency in existing buildings. Many rural areas are not connected to the gas grid. There is a UK incentive to introduce biomass boilers into homes (growing market in domestic level). The **experience** in the implementation of community energy initiatives could be applied for biogas. Key factor is to make the **technology** understandable to the people and promote its benefits to local community.

Success Factors

- **Renewable energy resources available in Scotland** – People and the government is very conscious of having many renewable energy resources not being exploited (wind, sun, hydroelectricity, biomass etc.)
- **The possible active participation of Energy4All, a non-profit social enterprise (co-operative) with best business practices** – Energy4All has the background and the facilities to support community (renewable) energy initiatives in terms of regulation, financing, planning, administration, communication etc.
- **The collaboration with a private developer like Falk Renewables Wind Ltd** – Falk Renewables has a technology expertise in Wind Parks and a good track record in distributing the profits to the shareholders
- **The choice of a democratic and transparent legal form** - A Co-operation Society is the legal form that follows key principles such as operating in a democratic manner i.e. one member one vote – regardless of how large or small a member's investment or the right for every member to be elected on the Board.
- **Positive public perception on renewable energy sources** – There is a growing interest in RES across UK. People are likely to support community (renewable) energy initiatives in opposition to the general governments' inadequate policy
- **Clear visibility in specific technologies** – Technologies like Wind and Solar are very visible to the public regarding their operational characteristics and their positive impact to the environment

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- **Rely on private developers to build the entire wind farm** - Different objectives make sometimes the communication between the **co-operation** and Falk Ltd problematic.
- **Negative tendency on onshore Wind Farms** - During the developing of the project, the board sometimes faced negative tendency of communities against onshore Wind Farms (fear of a negative impact to the tourism due to Wind Farm appearance). The co-operative overcame this issue focusing on community relations and giving clear information on the project and its benefits.
- **Unfavourable-unstable Policy and Legislation** – Community (renewable) energy project is a long term activity and frequent-(and sometimes unsupportive) changes in **legislation** put barriers to the development of Grassroots Community (renewable) energy initiatives. Initiatives that are supported by agencies like Energy4All are likely to overcome this problem easily.

- **Selling electricity directly to the customers is not allowed** – If Community (renewable) energy initiatives had the right to sell the electricity they produce directly to local customers that could make their projects financially more viable.
- **Lack of support to Grassroots Community (renewable) Energy Initiatives** – Issues like **regulation, financing, planning** and **collaboration** with third parties (e.g. land owners, local authorities) must be tackled by Grassroots community (renewable) energy initiatives themselves.
- **Limited role of local authorities** in the initiation of community (renewable) energy projects: Minimum role in planning approval of community energy initiatives.
- **Regulation and local authorities** – Local authorities are banned by regulation to participate in community energy initiatives.
- **Peoples` preference to the standard commercial model** – Individuals are in favour of standard commercial model (in implementing renewable energy initiatives).

Implications for Biogas

The exploitation of biomass and biogas potential of the region can increase the regional renewable energy potential. The regulation should be helpful in promoting community energy initiatives that are mostly suitable for the local area (wind, solar, biomass, biogas), engaging as more as possible local residents to receive the financial benefits. Additionally, the initiatives should be allowed to sell the energy directly to the public in lower prices (confronting energy poverty).

6.1.15 ZEZ Cooperative – Croatia

ZEZ is embedded into the **Cooperative for Ethical Financing**, which is going to set up the first **Ethical Bank** in Croatia (operational by the end of 2016).

Practice

The idea is that they will employ the ethical bank in managing their **investments** and supporting **local communities and local cooperatives** in gathering an initial equity and financing their own energy projects. Their ultimate goal/vision is to move beyond consulting and set up their own 100% renewable-based electricity supply. ZEZ is already working on their first renewable project(s) for which they're setting up crowd-funding schemes. They are not focused in one type of renewable energy; rather they are pursuing wind, solar, hydro, and biogas/biomass.

Every member of the coop has one voice (vote) in the decision-making. There is a General assembly (all members, once a year), which decides on **strategic course of action, approves financial plan, chooses cooperative management and advisory board**, etc. There is also a cooperative manager (interviewee) that runs the coop on a daily basis. For decisions of higher importance the manager takes permission from the advisory board and for crucial decision he has to take permission from the assembly. The coop can have a more or **less "horizontal" governance** structure. For example, there can be one big investor that has more control over the whole organization. However, in the general assembly every member has one vote. But if you have more shares you get bigger part of the profit.

Success Factors

Motivation Mix

- An important reason that ZEZ adopted the **coop** model is that they want to decouple their profit (income) from feed-in-tariffs. The final goal is the maximization of **profit** on the final product, i.e. food. The cooperative model is known to farmers because agricultural **cooperatives** are still very much alive in Croatia and so it is not a difficult task to make them understand what all this is about or to convince them to join. Other factors, apart from **profit**, include **sustainability, ecology**, etc. but most people need to see the money first. And when it comes to profit people do not only focus on personal gain, but also common gain is important (profit for the community). In some communities the **mayors** are champions of participating in the cooperative so that they increase

local satisfaction and get re-elected. This happens mostly where mayors are independent from parties.

- The motivation for developers to be involved in the coop is **financial**. The banking sector in Croatia is unfavorable towards investments in the real economy and they prefer what they perceive as **secure investments** like real estate and tourism. Due to the fact that foreign investment groups now own all banks in Croatia, they have no interest on investments that will trigger local economic development. Furthermore, the interest rates are too high. So ZEZ is proposing the alternative model of financing a project through **crowd-investing** where developers are supported by equity partners all of which are included under the umbrella of the coop and therefore have a stake in the outcome. The idea behind this is that you make all the supply chain accountable by making them all dependent on the project's profit/success rather than relying on bilateral contractual agreements. In a nutshell, the developers are motivated to join the coop due to on the one hand unfavorable banking sector combined with high interest rates and on the other hand a financing solution (coop) that minimizes risk for them.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

Their biogas business model is aimed at enabling local agricultural cooperatives running their own biogas and CHP plants without the need for subsidies. This is still in the planning stage (feasibility study completed). ZEZ is currently focused on heat and electricity production through CHP. Using gas directly (either injection to grid or sell it as gas) is not in the immediate plans due to the grid not being adequately developed and the gas market in Croatia **lacking transparency**. Their business model incorporates principles of **circular economy**: they are not looking at how much they can sell, for example, the heat generated from the CHP; rather they're looking at how much this heat, when given free of charge back to the coop members, can increase their agricultural production and make their agro-business more **profitable**. So they expect to get a **return on investment** from the increased agricultural productivity of the coop's members. So, they are looking for biomass suppliers that are also potential heat consumers, for example big part of their production coming from greenhouses (that require heat). ZEZ calculates the increase of productivity that the use of heat will give the farmers (they wouldn't use heat otherwise because it's too expensive), and then they calculate the increase in the profitability of the farmers' business and this what they take the profitability of the biogas plant to be (i.e. equal to the increase of profitability of the core business of the suppliers/consumers).

Implications for Biogas

Their biogas business model is aimed at enabling local agricultural cooperatives running their own biogas and CHP plants without the need for subsidies. This is still in the planning stage (feasibility study completed). ZEZ is currently focused on heat and electricity production through CHP.

6.1.16 Danish Hashoej Biogas Cooperative – Denmark

Hashoej Biogas is a Danish cooperative that operates a biogas plant. All of the coop's members are farmers that supply the plant with manure and/or get back fertilizer after the manure is processed.

Practice

A **simple and relatively direct model** of governance is possible due to the small number of coop members (**33 members** in total). Although initially the company operated under a governance structure with a CEO, they later decided to shift all the management power to the coop members.

Success Factors

The **coop members collectively manage the cooperative**, although they have **elected 5 among them to form a management committee** that oversees the operation more closely. In addition they have hired a Biogas Plant manager (the interviewee).

Obstacles & Failure Factors

The facility is 22 years old. The interviewee does not know the story behind the creation of the coop or the original motivation of the founding members. The only thing he could reveal is that some farmers thought that it was a good idea to have a biogas plant. The interviewee did say that the plant

is **marginally profitable**, just enough for it to remain operational. Therefore the **coop members** do not receive any significant direct profit from the plant's operation, apart from receiving the free fertilizer. However, sending their manure to the biogas plant allows them to increase their own production. This is because there is a **law limiting** the amount of manure they can spread back to the fields. But having the biogas plant allows them to send their manure to the biogas plant and use the coop's lorries to distribute any spare manure or fertilizer to other farmers. Therefore they are free to increase their cattle size (and production) without having to return more manure to the fields.

The interviewee reported two types of problems: **Legislation** and **social**. With regard to the latter, they have encountered problems with neighbors because of noise (particularly from lorries transferring the manure back and forth) and smell. There are some times complaints of lorries driving fast or being heavy and destroying the road. With regard to legislation, they have to follow environmental rules and they are submitted to inspections from government officials who give them warning if something is wrong and they have to fix it for the next time they visit. The **environmental regulations** are dealt with by simply complying with **all laws and warnings**.

Implications for Biogas

The problems with the neighbours are dealt through constant engagement and taking action according to complaints. One final **regulation** that they have to follow relates to organic waste: 25% of the organic matter put in the biogas must be waste.

6.1.17 SVEF is a wind power cooperative – Sweden

SVEF is a wind power cooperative that gives the **opportunity to people to buy shares** in return for 1000 kWh of **electricity per year per share**. Each cooperative member can have as many shares as they need, depending on their annual electricity demands (in principle they could buy more shares than their electricity consumption but it wouldn't make sense to do so).

Practice

SVEF currently has about 2000 members with an average of 10 shares per member (i.e. a total of about 20.000 shares). SVEF has **10 power stations** and produced last year 45 GWh. 20GWh of their production went to their **cooperative members** and the rest was sold. Note that all of their production goes to the grid, they then buy back almost half of it for their members, and the rest is being sold to the energy supplier (or grid owner).

Success Factors

SVEF operates according to Swedish Law for Cooperatives. They have a general assembly of members once a year where the review last year's results, take important decisions, etc. In the assembly, each member gets one vote no matter how many shares they have. Note that this is **not obligatory**; they could have as many votes as shares. However, they do it this way because of historical reasons: when the cooperative started, 20 years ago, they established this system because **their target clientele were cottages and houses** which require only 1 or maximum 2 shares to cover their annual power needs. Later, bigger businesses (e.g. hotels) got interested and started buying more shares. But the **governance model** (of one vote per member) persisted without any objections. Hans (a founding member and president says that he also likes it this way. SVEF is one of about 50 cooperatives in Sweden with the same concept and same business (electricity from wind power) but SVEF's model of operation is not the norm.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

SVEF has to deal with some regulatory, tax-related, problems that the interviewee thinks are unique to former communist/socialist countries (!). According to him, the tax office **does not recognize the members' contributions to the cooperative** as part of their energy expenses. They only look at their annual energy bill, which is substantially lower than their actual consumption (since most of it is covered by the power they get through SVEF). But the tax office does not take into account that

although they appear to be paying very little money to the regular energy supplier, they have paid for most of their energy by participating in SVEF cooperative (note: due to the interviewees low level in English I am not sure I got this right). Another problem that SVEF faces is related to **market pressures**. Right now the electricity prices from regular energy suppliers are very low. Profit margins are getting slimmer for the whole industry. Furthermore, the wind-power installations in Sweden are still expanding which also drives prices down. So although the cost of installing and maintaining wind turbines has decreased, electricity prices are decreasing even more. So SVEF cannot further expand its operations if they are to have a balanced budget.

Implications for Biogas

Biogas is associated in Sweden mainly with transport fuel. The interviewee brought as example the city of Örebro (200.000 people) where they collect all the organic waste from the households and they send it to a community biogas plant that turns it to Biogas that is used to fuel all the Public Transport buses of the town (~200 buses).

6.1.18 Sharenergy Consulting Co-op – UK

Sharenergy is a co-op and helps communities setting up their own energy projects, including: assess the technical feasibility of their ideas, obtain planning permission for them, set up a co-operative to raise finance and run the scheme.

Practice

Most of the projects are then funded by the co-operatives through a community share offer, with returns of investment usually between 4 and 7%. Community share offers are also a key instrument to gain new members and to connect to the community. Sharenergy works across the technologies, with projects in wind, PV, biomass and hydro. If energy produced is the considered indicator, then the proportion of their projects is wind 50%, solar 35%, hydro 10%, biomass 5%. However other definitions of success for community energy projects exist, and can be in terms of member numbers, environmental impacts of the initiative (eg. Carbon reduction), publicity for renewables and mutual societies, policy impact, amount of community funds paid out.

Success Factors

When planning a renewable energy projects: start from what is available in your area, don't start from a pre-conceived favorite technology. Also, don't set up arbitrary boundaries of what would be the area of consideration – The parish might not be an effective boundary, is better to think in terms of bioregion, or in other terms, use both physical geography and human geography. Usually the initial planning is done together with local groups, with “open map sessions”: what can be done locally? People bring their ideas and knowledge of local resources and think collectively about the potential for renewable energy in their locality. Also is the good occasion to understand potential objections and try to find solutions.

Importance of the team. The team must be chosen, not just bring in whoever is up for it. A range of skills is needed, that complements idealism, which usually is the starting point. It is important to work with people who are already well connected and well known and trusted by the broader community – mentioned the case of successful fund raising for a wind project which figured the faces of well-known promoters on the promotional materials.

Importance of telling a story which people are interested in joining, a desirable vision of the future (it's an idea used by transition town movement). The vision should include the money – it is important to do a proper financial planning since the beginning and this in parallel with the various organizational and legal models, which can be adopted.

Ensure the support of the landowner, and get an agreement signed as soon as possible. Many cases of landowners removing support at later stage of the projects, just because they were never really engaged and finally just defended their own personal interest.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

- High risk on the future operation of the AD plant.
- Risk of ensuring a steady supply chain.
- Local authorities not supportive and not skilled.

6.2 Best Practices

Recommendations for the successful development of renewable energy programs and incentives:

There is an important precondition for the success of a community energy project. That is the **motivation mix**, which can be environmental and ecological, social and anthropocentric as well as economic. The **active involvement of a variety of stakeholders** (which could range, for example, from municipalities, authorities and policy makers, to cooperatives, renewable energy organizations, planning offices, funding bodies and local community members) can also influence significantly the success of a community energy project. Local stakeholders' interested often are driven by **economic benefits**. Therefore, following successful and profitable "**role model**" projects may gain their local trust and attract investments.

During community energy projects, **community members connect with experts** and increases their understanding of the methods followed to produce energy for their own community. Through **communication**, public acceptance is increased and obstacles can be overcome. Such obstacles can stem from multiple sources, such as community members, local stakeholders with conflicting interests, fear of economic risks and lack of support from intermediaries as well as paucity from policymakers.

Further to the 18 interviews carried out by the ISABEL partners (shown above), the following tables illustrate important success and failure factors identified.

Success Factors
Past
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful projects in the past • Following a successful (profitable) role model: To gain the trust of the local communities
Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support from renewable energy stakeholders and other initiatives • Academia and bioenergy networks • Benefits for its shareholders: a) possible annual return depending on profits, b) creation of jobs and c) reinvestment to the local economy.
Social Factors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target clientele • Active participation • Collaboration with a private developer • Democratic & transparent legal operations • Surplus fund for community energy efficiency projects • Willingness to use renewable energy

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability and professionalism of the municipal energy supplier • Jobs opportunities
Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication and transparency: Best way to deal with obstacles • Link project with tangible outcomes, such as food & health • Communication activities: Enhancing the public acceptance
Local core competences
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitive advantages of specific locations: capacity, price comparison to oil, gas
Financial
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost effectiveness • Security • "Sweeteners": To buy a part of a RES power plant for economic benefits • Financial (perceived secure investments) • Alternative financial models through crowd-investing • Self-funding • Surplus or profit to be re-directed to the community as capital for projects: Farmers financially benefitting from the system • Maximizing profit through sustainability, ecology driven initiatives
Perception
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive public perception on renewable energy sources • Familiarizing the benefits of RES use to funding bodies
Education
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of RES through school teaching
Governance & Legislation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance model • Transparent legal form: including cooperative culture and tradition, involvement of political parties in enhancing active participation of community members • Good knowledge of the legislation and the European community model experience • Local authorities collaboration
Techniques
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of technology • Regular information • Establishing a green energy approach • Optimum solution for a mix of renewables (solar/wind/wood chip/biogas with CHP for example) depending on planning constraints • A nutrient bank within the community: concept was to reduce the emissions to their environment.

Obstacles & Failure Factors

Private vs Public sector

- Rely on private developers
- Peoples` preference to the standard commercial model
- Lack of support from cooperatives
- Preconceptions in local community
- Lack of experienced organizations in supporting community initiatives in terms of business, finance and operation
- Competitive rivalry & Conflict of interests (oil&gas vs RES suppliers)

Legal, Policymaker, Authority & Governmental Barriers

- Funding to support sustainable energy projects is now much reduced.
- Political and legal frameworks
- Rules & Legislation barriers
- Policy makers: one-size fits all approach
- Political framework: Change/end of supporting renewable energy, lobbying is necessary
- Political framework: End of financial support of RE, especially bioenergy
- Missing initiative of the municipal authorities
- Lack of provision for tax-reliefs
- Unfavourable-unstable Policy and Legislation – Community (renewable) energy in legislation put barriers to the development of Grassroots Community.
- Legal constrain, lack of understanding of the technology & red tape
- Lack of support to Grassroots Community (renewable) Energy Initiatives
- Limited role of local authorities in the initiation of community (renewable) energy projects: Minimum role in planning approval of community energy initiatives.
- Regulation and local authorities – Local authorities are banned by regulation to participate in community energy initiatives.
- Inability of the public authorities to properly support CE RES initiatives
- Choice of location for renewable energy plant: Statutory requirements

Social

- Lack of awareness: Fear that composting is *smelly*
- Lacking transparency
- Negative tendency towards RES
- Lack of willingness to participate
- Citizens local conflicts

Financial

- High 'up front 'costs, paying for local energy network and structural surveys
- Sourcing enough local food waste: Problem of accessibility
- Authorities signing up long-term contracts with councils for the removal of food waste that cannot be legally broken to allow feed stock for small scale operations.
- Risks
- Planning and budgeting
- Missing financial support of district heating networks
- Declining income from the gas or electricity in terms of the Feed in Tariffs and renewable energy incentives

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lack of financial support and subsidies• Decreases tax-reliefs
Communication
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Breaking the existing circle of the supply chain and operational method: Farmers were reluctant to participate• Lack of trust in the technical standards• Environmental legislation for project and licensing as initially the biomass power plant was licensed for erection and operation in a specific purchased land while the pellet plant was not• Involvement of relevant authorities
Technical issues
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Project feasibility analysis (region may not have enough biomass)• Lack of support for transport of local feedstock: Failing to get planning permission• Lack of adequate energy infrastructure• Lack of measuring and monitoring renewable energy capacity
Stakeholders
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lack of acceptance of the stakeholders the new incentive's economic risks: Mental barriers

7. Conclusions & Implications for Biogas

Conclusions

This report presents a literature review with selected examples of social innovation, community energy and their combination in a variety of projects. As there is currently no “single prescription to success” of these projects, the focus of this study was to explore specific practices and the success and failure factors of community energy projects. The findings are further supported by interviews of 18 stakeholders interviewed in March 2016. The interviewed stakeholders’ organizations are based in Europe (namely Greece, Germany, UK, Denmark and Croatia) and ISABEL partners discussed with them specifically *the key success factors, obstacles overcome as well as types of renewable energy and community energy models implemented in their region.*

The interviews highlighted that **cross-sector partnerships and synergetic actions** can stimulate successful social innovation community energy projects. Good practices suggested would seem to combine local entrepreneurial activities (e.g. farmers’), municipalities, local authorities, academia and local businesses. Joining these and more can create networks and cooperatives. The benefit of such **cooperative memberships** is largely perceived to be socio-economic, with environmental elements as the base point of project development. More specifically, these projects were shown to stimulate communities to **generate and own** their energy supply chain, achieve **energy self-sufficiency**, promote **sustainable ecology**, and thereafter become **shareholders** of their local community biogas energy venture and increase their joint **profitability**. Cooperative ventures are based on equity, which helps render the community investments and financing as ethical. Successful projects appeared to raise awareness and interest in alternative energy use and benefits, which could influence further the support of local and **regional authorities**.

Success factors in social innovation community energy projects

Although the **motivation mix** (for environmental and socio-economic benefits) forms an important baseline for the decision to start a community energy project, there is a more profound factor that can drive active engagement. That is **communication**. Investing time and effort in communicating energy challenges, local core competences and energy capacities can reveal the benefits of the proposed community energy venture through social innovation. Communication can be face-to-face but also through social media and gaming. Through a variety of methods, it can increase transparency, raise awareness (e.g. of the benefits of using biomass for energy production), link projects with tangible outcomes and enhance public acceptance. Good communication is crucial for the success of community energy projects. The 18 interviews of the ISABEL project, along with the literature review, demonstrated that communication can also often resolve many obstacles found in community energy projects. This can be through providing sufficient information to local stakeholders about the benefits of community energy, which will effectively minimize their fear of economic risks through, for example, the presentation of **financial “sweeteners”** (farmers benefiting from the initiative). The main benefit of stakeholder engagement in social innovation community energy projects is **annual financial returns** and the opportunity to create their own supply chain. Reinvesting annual profits in the local economy can further boost the development of such projects and enhance the creation of **new jobs**.

Obstacles and ways to overcome them

Intermediaries, policymakers as well as **governments** have been shown often to cast detrimental effects to project initiation, realization and success. The paucity of policymakers, overgeneralizations drawn by intermediaries and governmental legislation may impede the inclusion of alternative energy sources in community energy ventures. This can be exacerbated by a lack of provision of **tax-reliefs and subsidies**, which would otherwise promote project initiation (see motivation mix). Establishing partnerships between a wide diversity of stakeholders in order to overcome long-standing socio-economic barriers was therefore almost unanimously proposed by the ISABEL project interviewees and found in the examples explored in the literature. **Governmental and policy barriers** could be overcome if existing successful **role models** were introduced in the proposed community energy initiatives.

The intersection however between **the public and private sector** can also present a barrier to community energy projects, due to **competitive rivalries** and **conflicts of interest** (e.g. with oil and gas suppliers). Tackling those barriers may be more demanding and may relate to politics or market entry questions.

Finally, there may be **technical** obstacles also faced during the initiation of a project, which should be resolved prior or during its start. These may relate to **infrastructure** and the project **feasibility** and in some cases may require the development of a new supply chain.

Conclusions on Implications for Biogas

<i>Implications for Biogas</i>	
Community Benefits	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The community will understand the core competencies and energy capacities of its location • Local people awareness will be raised in terms of the benefit of their involvement in the ownership of their biogas scheme • Bioenergy: People will appreciate to use their private biomass in their local heating network • Gain a sophisticated approach to community engagement and networking for community biogas projects 	
Financial Benefits	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The community gains financial self-control and ownership • With the end of feed-in-tariffs, energy efficiency and shared savings can be achieved 	
Social Engagement	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To increase the engagement of citizens in the company's shareholder scheme and establish an integrated model of household waste management by: • Biogas plant utilising household organic matter as well as agricultural and livestock residues in order to produce electricity and fertilizers • Promoting the concept of gathering vegetable oil from schools, which the company will purchase to support the schools' heating problem • Setting up sanitary waste landfills, where the limited residue is going to be disposed • Exploiting the biomass and biogas potential of the region, which can increase the regional renewable energy potential • Their biogas business model is aimed at enabling local agricultural cooperatives running their own biogas and CHP plants without the need for subsidies • Taking action according to complaints 	
Technical Developments	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presenting new techniques, explain changing prices, discuss everything what is important for the involved people 	

Appendix 1: Basic Concepts of Social Innovation

A broadly applicable processes of social innovation is based on a step-by-step

- Formation of a group identity
- Establishment of leaders (individuals or groups) that will work on the specific mission
- Reframing of the given problem that will be approached in a new way
- Engagement of stakeholders

Elements that compose socially innovative approaches (cf. Caulier et al., 2012)¹⁰⁵ relate to the

- Novelty of the project (e.g. according to the corresponding sector, region, market, user)
- Clear transition from promising ideas to practical implementation (in a sustainable way)
- Empowerment of the society to restructure its roles and relations in order to develop new environmental strategies for a better use of resources and more
- Method of addressing and successfully meeting a specific social need

Investigation factors¹⁰⁶ (cf. explored by Biggs et al., 2010) defining the procedure of social innovation in ecosystem management and renewable energy projects can be summarized as follows:

- Context & triggers for innovation
- Social entrepreneurship
- Form
- New perspectives & reframing
- Engaging stakeholders
- Institutional support
- Diffusion

These factors are central to the social innovation processes, which aim to identify “triggers” for innovation (existing and new ideas) as well as methods of “incubating” and spreading new ideas throughout the society (diffusion and contagion). In the environmental sector, these factors serve also as facilitators of the transformation from centralized sectorial approaches to adaptive and collaborative ones.

In cases of nature resource management for sustainable environmental and economic outcomes the stages¹⁰⁷ of social innovation may describe the evolutionary concept of a so-called “social capital”. This concept proposes that social networks have a certain value or “capital”¹⁰⁸, which is derived from the collaboration between different individuals, groups or networks. Social capital is based on issues of mutual trust, reciprocity and exchange, common rules (including, norms and sanctions) and connectedness. Based on these issues, Pretty & Ward (2001) suggest that social innovation projects can successfully meet challenges of renewable energy use and sustainable development. Ultimately, by incorporating the evolutionary process of social capital¹⁰⁹, social innovation in renewable energy use and sustainable development can be described in the following three stages.

- Reactive (dependence)
- Realization (dependence)
- Awareness (independence)

In the reactive stage, a group acknowledges the need for a change, for instance in order to improve agricultural methods and techniques to reduce costs and use of pesticides. Thereafter, in the realization

¹⁰⁵ Caulier-Grice, J., Davies, A., Patrick, R., Norman, W. (2012). Defining Social Innovation. Part One of *Social Innovation Overview: A deliverable of the project: “The theoretical, empirical and policy foundations for building social innovation in Europe” (TEPSIE)*, European Commission – 7th Framework Programme, Brussels: European Commission, DG Research. Available at: <http://youngfoundation.org/publications/tepsie-social-innovation-overview-parts-i-ii-iii-iv-and-bibliography>

¹⁰⁶ Biggs, R., Westley, F.R. & Carpenter, S.R. (2010). Navigating the Back Loop: Fostering Social Innovation and Transformation in Ecosystem Management. *Ecology and Society*. 15:2 (9).

¹⁰⁷ Pretty, J. & Ward, H. (2001). Social Capital and the Environment. *World Development*. 29(2):209–227.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid ¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁹ Ibid ¹⁰⁷

stage, the group develops new solutions that are incorporated (realized) in their existing technologies. For example, this could involve harvesting rainwater for toilet flushing or using manure to fertilize the crops rather than importing fertilizers for farming. In the last stage, the group becomes aware of its collective capacity and can finally spread its knowledge and innovative techniques to other groups or communities.

The application of local knowledge through community and social action is in effect the essential element of social innovation. According to the SPREAD¹¹⁰ Sustainable Lifestyles 2050 project, social innovators (individuals and or communities) are “the gatekeepers” towards more sustainable lifestyles. That is because they can test small scale initiatives, which thereafter can be scaled up to much larger participatory planning incentives. An example of the latter can be found in Denmark and Austria where grassroots entrepreneurs and do-it-yourself builders developed simple technologies for solar collection and wind power generation¹¹¹, which could thereafter be developed commercially.

One of the key benefits of social innovation is that it offers an effective bottom-up approach in tackling multifaceted issues. This type of approach can improve¹¹²:

- Public trust
- Local decision-making & experimentation
- Social norms, values and practices

¹¹⁰ <http://www.sustainable-lifestyles.eu>

¹¹¹ Ornetzeder, M. & Rohracher, H. (2013). Of solar collectors, wind power, and car sharing: Comparing and understanding successful cases of grassroots innovations. *Global Environmental Change*. 23(5):856– 867.

¹¹² http://ec.europa.eu/research/innovation-union/index_en.cfm

Appendix 2: Best Practices in Renewable Energy (literature survey)

Currently, there are numerous *breeding grounds* for enhanced energy efficiency across the EU, with Denmark¹¹⁴ being one of pioneering nations in energy conservation. Planning for energy efficiency in communities is a complex and multi-faceted task. This task relates to a number of external and internal, national and regional, as well as sector-based factors, which further relate to renewable energy incentives.

Table 1 illustrates a few important sectors, which appear to offer **examples of good practices of renewable energy use across Europe**. It suggests specifically that amongst all sectors (and players), the buildings, transport and governance sectors are targeted for more exemplary practice examples in renewable energy use.

Remarkably, the building sector's energy consumption in the EU accounts for more than 40% of the total energy consumption¹¹⁵. The transport sector is associated with 20% of the total EU greenhouse gas emissions. Promoting behavioural change towards building energy consumption may offer significant benefits.

Further to these three sectors, the public, industry & tertiary as well as appliances sectors appear also to offer good examples in renewable energy use across Europe¹¹⁶.

Source¹¹³

Table 1. Good & Best Practices of RES categorized by nation and by sector.

GOOD & BEST PRACTICES OF RES BY NATION AND SECTOR						
NATION	SECTOR					
	Appliances	Buildings	Governance	Industry & Tertiary	Public	Transport
Austria	✓					
Bulgaria			✓			
Denmark		✓	✓			
Estonia		✓				
Finland					✓	✓
France			✓			
Germany		✓				
Netherlands	✓				✓	
Slovenia						✓
Sweden				✓		
UK		✓		✓		✓

APPLIANCES SECTOR

<i>Austria</i>	klima:aktiv, providing incentives for the installation of energy efficient appliances
<i>Netherlands</i>	EU Energy Labelling Directive implemented & online services informing costumers about RES (e.g. EnergyWeter.nl, MillieuCentraal)

¹¹³ <http://www.bioregions.eu/>

¹¹⁴ <http://www.eeb.org/EEB/?LinkServID=30CC2E6A-D8B0-0495-BA4A5F7B9A45C403&showMeta=0>

¹¹⁵ Ibid ⁴⁸

¹¹⁶ Ibid ⁴⁸

BUILDINGS' SECTOR

The buildings' sector accounts for a substantial proportion of the EU total energy consumption, thus the 2010 EU Directives have highlighted this importance of energy efficiency in buildings and offers new standards for the construction of new buildings and retrofitting existing ones. Some good examples identified relate to the policy mix and Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS)¹¹⁷. The policy mix in these cases appears to follow a specific structure, which includes information tools, education & training, regulatory measures for 'smart' spatial planning, energy performance standards & certificates as well as tax breaks & subsidies. Good practices in the building sector are identified in:

<i>Denmark</i>	Energy Pioneer on MEPS & early adopters of Energy Performance Certification MEPS in Denmark are supported by strict & voluntary standards.
<i>Estonia</i>	MEPS (since 2008) for new buildings and retrofitting existing ones & offering Energy certificates <u>Supporting financially retrofits & renovations through:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loans. • Tax deduction of interest paid for loans. • Subsidies for retrofits & renovations that may amount up to 35% of total project costs. • Energy audits <u>Educating professionals:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Architects and Civil engineers. • Construction workers. <u>Constructing exemplary buildings in the public sector following:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standards for low-energy building.
<i>Germany</i>	Policy mix (through Federal Law) for regularly tightened MEPS & offering Energy Certificates Focusing in new buildings and retrofitting existing ones. Encouraging RE for heating. <u>Sponsoring:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficient building construction. • Energy audits.
UK	MEPS mission for zero-carbon residential projects from 2016 onwards & Focusing overall in housing stock (new & existing) <u>Supporting:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New energy efficient heating systems, insulation and draught proof system through the <i>Warm Front Scheme</i>, which is offered to households spending more than 10% of their income on heating. • Energy savings through the "Green Deal" Framework that is addressed to companies offering an investment free energy improvement to home-owners who will thereafter profit from the financial value of energy savings. • Design improvements to achieve higher energy efficiency (e.g. BREEAM Excellent).

¹¹⁷ Ibid ⁴⁸

GOVERNANCE SECTOR

<i>Bulgaria</i>	<p>Targets to halve its 2005 energy intensity by 2020 Implementing both top-down and bottom-up approaches</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple stakeholders involved in policy-making • Municipalities supporting • Tower retrofitting programmes • Energy services
<i>Denmark</i>	<p>Danish Energy Agency supporting goals for energy efficiency & Centre for Energibesparelser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting financially private (e.g. household), public sector and enterprises • Tax hikes on implemented energy efficient schemes (e.g. related to fossil energy)
<i>France</i>	<p>Implemented the Energy Efficiency Certificate (EEC, since 2005) & Long-term top-down and bottom-up strategies involving:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple stakeholders, such as NGOs, employers, unions, municipalities. This involvement achieved a wide acceptance of goals for energy efficiency. • ADEME (National Energy Agency) coordinating & facilitating energy saving strategies. • EEC relates to a financially beneficial scheme to support energy savings through the employment of energy service companies that will be paid by financial value of the energy savings achieved. • Developing individual's energy saving tool (providing estimations of individual developments energy consumption/ energy efficiency).

INDUSTRY & TERTIARY SECTOR

<i>Sweden</i>	Programme for improving energy efficiency in energy intensive industry (PFE)
<i>UK</i>	Carbon Reduction Commitment (CRC) (subject to scrutiny)

PUBLIC SECTOR

<i>Finland</i>	<p>Local Government Energy Efficiency Agreement, focusing in public buildings (owned by the central government) & strict MEPS for new buildings and retrofitting existing ones.</p> <p><u>Sponsoring:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy saving • Energy audits
<i>Netherlands</i>	<p>Public Procurement Expertise Centre (PIANOo) supporting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable public procurement for more than 45 products. • Since the beginning of 2016, all government agencies and public bodies should insist on making sustainable purchases in order to increase the total energy savings potential (current estimate is above TWh).

TRANSPORT SECTOR

UK	Offering the 'Low Sustainable Transport Fund' through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cooperation of municipalities and local stakeholders.
<i>Slovenia</i>	Improving the public transportation competitiveness by a socially Innovative scheme, which offers subsidies depending on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The purchase of lower carbon-intensive vehicles (e.g. using natural gas). • The number of passenger distance covered through public transport. • The use of public transport for commuting to work.
<i>Finland</i>	Implementing policies that increase public interest towards cycling and walking by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxation according to vehicle's CO₂ emissions. • Including in the drivers' education the concept of energy efficient driving.

"Methods & Tools"

The methods and measures of energy efficiency are generally structured upon a bottom-up or top-bottom approach. Horizontal measures (HM) may couple these approaches and include voluntary activities as well as the engagement of multiple stakeholders in a variety of communities. HMs relate for instance, with infrastructure services or strategic and support activities and offer a useful tool for improving the coordination between communities or nations¹¹⁸.

The French government has introduced a tool to estimate energy savings based on the analysis of individual measures.

¹¹⁸ <http://ec.europa.eu/idabc/en/document/5012/5584.html>

Appendix 3: Interview Questions

Key Factors for Stakeholder Interviews

General:

- Please offer a comprehensive description of the initiative (e.g. the initiative's history, vision, concept and current condition (aims accomplished, maturity, etc.), as well as legal status (cooperative, etc.), operational structure, best practices, methods, future plans, and more)
- What kind of renewable energy sources (RES) are being used in your region and for what purpose? (e.g. heating)

Success, Failure & Obstacles

(Note for the Interviewer: This section should include information on: policy-making and regulations, financial, and technical issues, supply chain and operational issues, social awareness and perception, etc.)

- What are the key factors that constitute a successful community energy project in your region? Why?
- What are the main or common failure factors? Why?
- What are the obstacles faced?
- Are obstacles generally overcome? Which ones? With which methods?
- What challenges frequently occur?

Practices, Methods & Techniques

- Currently, which community energy practices (projects and approaches) are mostly used in your region? (e.g. solar energy, wind, biomass, etc.) Why?
- Which are the best and most effective community energy practices (approaches) in your region? Why?
- Which practices can increase your regional renewable energy potential?
- What are the best appropriate methods to apply the maximum energy potential in your community? (These, for example, could increase revenue through community measures, the use of RES or selling the energy produced, or other)
- Are there any existing techniques (applied, for example, by local authorities) available to harvest renewable energy through the involvement of the local community? (This may relate to the supply chain)
- Are there any passive practices used in order to reduce the need of energy consumption in your region? (e.g. relating to social innovation practices, involvement of local authorities, communities, etc.) Which ones?
- Are there any active measures taken to promote energy efficiency through new methods and tools in your region? (e.g. energy systems) Which ones?
- Are there any appropriate energy infrastructures, which can be adjusted, to use fuels and generate energy through biomass? (e.g. heating, transport)
- Are there any incentives for "green energy" (RES) that offer adequate subsidies or other measures to pursue community energy projects?
- In your region, are there any national or regional initiatives that promote the use of biogas or other RES? Which ones? To what extent are they pursued?
- Are there any existing community energy initiatives and practices that can be applied for biogas?

Additional Questions & Comments